

Project acronym: RESISTIRÉ

Project title: "RESponding to outbreaks through co-creaTive sustainable inclusive equality stRatEgies"

Grant agreement number: 101015990

Start date of project: 1 April 2021, Duration: 24 months

RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

Deliverable 5.2

Report on open studios cycle 1

Due date of deliverable	31/10/2021
Submission date	29/10/2021
File Name	D5.2 RESISTIRÉ Report on open studios cycle 1
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable	YW
Author name(s)	Aart Kerremans (YW), Igor Živković (YW), Alain Denis (YW) with contributions from Grace Romeo (YW), Philip De Wulf (YW), Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), Nazlı Türker (SU), Dag Balkmar (ORU) and Anne-Charlott Callerstig (ORU)
Revision number	01
Status	Final ¹
Dissemination Level	PU ²

¹ Document will be a draft until it is approved by the coordinator

² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Revision history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	19/10/2021	Aart Kerremans, Alain Denis	First draft
0.2	20/10/2021	YW	Second draft
0.3	21/10/2021	YW	Draft for internal review
0.4	26/10/2021	Rana Charafeddine, SU and ORU	Internal quality review and review by core partners
0.5	27/10/2021	Partners	Internal review by all partners
0.6	28/10/2021	YW (A. Denis, P. De Wulf)	Comments integrated

Partners

ESF
ORU
YW
OBU
K&I
TUD
SU
UDEUSTO
ISAS
Sciensano

Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101015990.

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List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
EU-27	European Union (27 countries)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OS	Open Studio
WLB	Work-Life Balance
WP	Work Package

Summary

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 31 countries (EU-27 plus Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. It does so by collecting policy data, quantitative data and qualitative data, and by analysing and translating these to insights to be used for designing, devising and piloting solutions for improved policies and social innovations to be deployed by policymakers, stakeholders and actors in the field in different policy domains. The project relies on a ten-partner multidisciplinary and multisectoral European consortium, and a well-established network of researchers in 31 countries.

This report provides an overview of the four Open Studios that were conducted in the first cycle of the RESISTIRÉ project and their respective results. The Open Studios constitute the co-creation step in the RESISTIRÉ process, with results from the first research cycle (WP2-4) being interpreted in this multidisciplinary format. The Open Studios are action-oriented, which means that their ultimate output consists of ideas for concrete action (which can be put into practice through pilot projects), input for recommendations to reshape policies, and unanswered questions (missing insights or knowledge) that can form the foundation of a future research agenda.

Four Open Studios were organised with a mix of participants from the consortium (12) and invited participants (8). Each Open Studio (OS) had a different thematic focus: the first OS focused on the impacts that healthcare workers endured, during the pandemic, and how to support them better in the future. The second OS looked at the increasing prevalence of telework, as well as how to make it more inclusive and compatible with the needs of employees. The third OS focused on the inequalities present in the use of green commons during the lockdown periods and how we can learn from this to make green spaces more inclusive and adaptable to everyone's needs. Finally, the fourth OS looked at masculinity roles, how they changed (or didn't) during the pandemic, and how they can be transformed for the better.

During two days, participants went through a creative process inspired by 'better stories' and by personas that were prepared for each Open Studio based on results of the research activities of the project. The result is a set of 27 action-ideas that will be further used and developed in the RESISTIRÉ project to:

- Formulate recommendations towards different target groups including policymakers, civil society organisations (including NGOs), employers, and other kinds of stakeholders.
- Launch pilot actions that will test and demonstrate the potential of innovative approaches.
- Feed the research agenda of RESISTIRÉ (the second cycle of research activities) and beyond.

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Introduction

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 31 countries (EU-27 plus Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. The pandemic has led to the introduction of national policy responses and measures in multiple policy domains to slow infections and prevent deaths (Cibin et al., 2021). This has profoundly changed lives, with physical and social distancing becoming the new norm and, where needed, quarantining and self-isolation. It has radically shifted how society is organised, with increased working from home, home-schooling and intensification of online presence, all with their own specific (un)intended consequences (Bonaccorsi et al., 2020). It has also meant furloughing and job losses, with associated economic hardship and mental health issues, delayed ordinary health treatments, and worse, the loss of life (Nicola et al., 2020; Van Bavel, 2020; Lewnard & Lo, 2020). And it has meant increases in the levels of gender-based violence and variations in access to support and healthcare.

The impacts of these developments, like those of other crises, are gendered and related to sex, age, disability, ethnicity/race, migration status, religion, social class, and the intersections between these inequalities (Lokot & Avakyan, 2020; Walter & McGregor, 2020; Walby, 2015). They are uneven and unequal, disproportional in their consequences for different groups, and their long-term impacts are uncertain (Cumming et al., 2020). Women have been disproportionately infected by COVID-19 (Sciensano, 2020) and affected by its impact; as front-line workers, as formal or informal caregivers in society; as exposed to a higher risk of men's violence, in particular as intimate partner violence. As these positions intersect with social class, ethnicity, age and other inequalities, our approach deploys a 'gender+' approach, which highlights gender relations and gender inequalities, but always considers how these intersect with other complex inequalities (Verloo, 2013; Walby et al., 2012). Policy responses to the pandemic also need to consider the gender+ perspective, and how some groups benefit, while others lose out. It is important to understand how different policy responses are having unequal effects, but also how different responses can be put into place to understand and address gender and intersectional inequalities in different policy domains (Lombardo & Kantola, 2019).

To meet these aims, RESISTIRÉ conducts policy analysis, as well as quantitative and qualitative research activities, to inform the design of innovative solutions. In this way, it responds to the outbreak through co-created and inclusive strategies that address old and new, durable and temporary inequality patterns in and across policy domains. The overall methodology of RESISTIRÉ is based on a step-by-step process running in three cycles over 24 months (April 2021/March 2023). All project activities are organised in these three cycles, feeding results into one another (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: RESISTIRÉ methodological step-by-step three cycle process

This report provides an overview of the four Open Studios that were conducted in the first cycle of the RESISTIRÉ project and their respective results. The Open Studios were organised online, had a duration of two full days each and took place from the end of September to mid-October 2021. The Open Studios constitute the co-creation step in the RESISTIRÉ process, with results from the previous steps (WP2-4) being interpreted in this multidisciplinary co-design format. This specific approach is a technique developed to design policies in a participative way by bringing together multiple kinds of expertise. The Open Studios are action-oriented, which means that their ultimate output consists of ideas for concrete action (which can be put into practice through pilot projects), input for recommendations to reshape policies, and unanswered questions (missing insights or knowledge) that can form the foundation of a future research agenda.

In the next chapter, the four Open Studios are described. The chapter starts with a description of the approach and how the Open Studios were prepared. After that, each individual Open Studio and its main themes, core issues, and relevant inequalities are briefly described. In a following chapter, the output that came out of the Open Studios that is relevant for the next steps of RESISTIRÉ's process is reported upon in three sections: operational recommendations for policymakers and other stakeholders, followed by the actions that could be used for pilot projects as well as ideas and recommendations for the future research agenda of RESISTIRÉ. The action-ideas described in this chapter are descriptions of the actions as they came out of the Open Studios, without any check for feasibility or improvements by the editors. They are considered as the output from the Open Studios that serves as input for the tasks in a next

work package (WP6) where they will be screened and, if selected, further developed and finetuned. Two more conclusive sections are a part of this deliverable: the lessons we learned from this first cycle of Open Studios and brief (preliminary) conclusions.

Four Open Studios

Open Studio approach

The Open Studios should be considered an action-oriented analysis of the research results of the previous steps of the project. The output consists of ideas for concrete action, input for recommendations to reshape policies, and questions that still need to be answered (missing insights or knowledge). The Open Studios approach is a technique developed to design policies in a participative way bringing together multiple expertise, including the user experience. The original concept, as described in Boyer, Cook and Steinberg (2011), had a duration of five full days. The Open Studio approach used in RESISTIRÉ is for two days given the scope of the issues covered and the feasibility of recruitment of participants. During an Open Studio, participants go through periods of divergence (exploring in an open way, brainstorming) and of convergence (bringing ideas together into concepts of potential solutions). Different exercises shape this process as described in the table below.

Overview of Open Studio:

DAY 01	TIME	INPUT / TOOLS	OBJECTIVE	OUTPUT
01 Warmup; getting started	9:15-10:30	Participant profiles	Familiarize participants with one another and with the OS approach. Get participants thinking beyond their own experience (considering target groups).	Examples of long-term impacts, both individual and structural
02 Inspiration	10:45-13:00	<i>Presentation on inequalities, set of inspiring / promising policy and societal responses</i>	Have participants look critically at previous responses to issues (indirectly) caused by COVID-19 to understand what has been done and what can be done better. What have been the better stories of responding to the pandemic (policy & initiative)? Ask participants to critically assess the provided policy and societal responses.	Common characteristics of better stories and their shortcomings: initial identification of opportunities; What/who is missing in the existing better stories?
03 Empathy	14:00-15:15	Impacts (01) and responses (02); <i>personas</i>	What/who would have made a difference for this persona? What would have been their better story? What kinds of support mechanisms, resources or actions would have helped?	Identification of additional gaps and opportunities/ideas for action
04 Brainstorm	15:30-17:00	Opportunities (02+03); <i>Lotus Blossom</i>	Develop ideas on how to overcome barriers creating inequalities and how to enable a more inclusive and creative response to the pandemic.	A selection of ideas to be characterised; Who/what is missing?
DAY 02	TIME	INPUT / TOOLS	OBJECTIVE	OUTPUT
05 Brainstorm	9:15-10:30	All ideas from day 1; <i>Mind map</i>	Idea generation - how to improve the story: insert theme challenge in the form of a probing question or description of a problem that stands out.	A selection of ideas to be characterised; Open questions for the research agenda; Who/what is missing?
06 Co-create	11:00-12:30	Ideas selected from 04+05	Turning ideas into better stories of societal responses	Potential pilot actions; Recommendations for stakeholders
07 Co-create	13:30-15:00	Ideas selected from 04+05	Turning ideas into better stories of policy responses	Potential pilot actions; Recommendations for stakeholders

08 Conclusions	15:15-17:00	Open for conclusion	Define priorities and follow-up actions	Priorities for stakeholder recommendations and for pilot actions
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The technique of personas is used to stimulate creativity, create empathy and to take some distance from the personal experience of the participants. These personas are based on the earlier research and profile different archetypes of people that were affected by the pandemic in one way or another.

Another technique used to inspire is the use of 'better stories' as explained in the next section.

Four Open Studios are planned for each cycle (twelve in total), which are held either face-to-face or online depending on the development of COVID-19 in the period when they must take place. Choosing a face-to-face workshop over an online one (or vice versa) will not have an impact on the general structure and content of an Open Studio. For the four Open Studios of the first cycle, held in September and October 2021, the consortium opted for an online format.

Preparing the Open Studios

Choice of themes

The reflection on the thematic focus of the Open Studios started mid-July 2021, still during the research activities of cycle 1 of the project. Open Studios need to have a clear goal and a scope that is compatible with the method: sufficiently broad to allow for creativity, but also sufficiently focused to ensure concrete results will come out. The selection of subjects was done in steps, with a long list, which led to a shortlist and finally a choice. The decision was taken to have different themes for all four OS and to mix OS with a target group focus and OS with a thematic focus.

The long list of 13 potential themes was established by the "Open Studio team" consisting of staff of YW, ORU and SU, based on the research results available³. This long list was reduced to seven by the same theme and shared with the whole consortium on 26 July through an online white board (Miro) as part of a two-step decision-making process. Each of the seven themes was described on the board: scope, sub-themes, target groups, relevant inputs from policy responses and from societal responses, profile of participants and motivation for the proposal. For the first step, partners were asked to add comments, make proposals of additions, suggest sub-themes or even a different focus. The second step was a voting based on a consensus by partner, using criteria that were also mentioned on the white board. These criteria take into account the Open Studio method, its advantages but also limitations: the feasibility to handle the theme within the format, the likeliness to get operational results; the

³ Main sources: ad hoc analysis of the reports from 8 expert workshops that were organised in June 2021 with experts on inequalities (8 different inequality domains) and of the reporting from national researchers on societal initiatives and policy reactions.

balance of themes covered in the four OS and the risk factor. Risk was considered as something the project should be ready to take as the purpose is to learn from the experience and the safest route should not always be chosen.

The final decision was taken by the teams of YW, SU and ORU, after a workshop where all consortium members were present (10 August 2021). The four themes selected were: "Impact on healthcare workers", "Challenge for the future: telework", "Access to green commons", and "Transformation of gender roles". The actual titles of the Open Studios evolved in the next weeks and are mentioned below.

Recruitment of participants

The decision on the themes triggered the recruitment of participants, both from within the consortium and invited experts. The target was to have 12 participants from team members of consortium members and to invite 8 external participants. For external participants, the target was to have a mix of different profiles: people directly involved professionally, people who had been studying the thematic area (mostly from academia and some from CSOs/NGOs), people with a creative/artistic background, people working for social partner organisations, and policymakers.

Identification of experts was a collective responsibility, with all consortium partners contributing to develop a long list for each OS. The YW team complemented this list through online searches to identify stakeholders and experts which were screened. Based on this long list, invitation mails were sent out in waves to ensure the quota agreed would be met as adequately as possible. The YW team was in charge of sending out invitations and coordinating the recruitment process. ESF was involved in contracting the external participants as experts.

Better Stories and Personas

In parallel, the content of the Open Studios and material to be used in the exercises were prepared. This was done through the exploitation of the research results from WP2, WP3 and WP4 which became available during August and September. The YW team prepared notes on the main inequalities linked to the theme and the potential core issues to be handled during the OS. These notes were shared with SU and ORU to get feedback and make final choices.

"Better stories" are used as inspiration in the Open Studios. These better stories are stories that identify how a given (negative) societal situation can be ameliorated to improve on existing practices, without being a perfect fix that turns out to be unattainable (i.e., a 'best story'). As feminist scholar Dina Georgis (2013) argues in her book *The Better Story*: "There is always a better story than the better story." The better stories served to inspire and form the groundwork for the development of more concrete results, like policy recommendations and potential societal initiatives. In this regard, the Open Studios tried to find answers to some

key questions, which included the following: What have been some inspiring practices, initiatives, and policies that we have been able to observe in different contexts across Europe? What can we learn from them to imagine even better stories of responding to this crisis that we all share, but are not equally affected by? How can a gender+ perspective help us explore, make visible, and co-create more egalitarian and inclusive policies, initiatives, and practices? The better stories were selected from the grids with policies and societal responses collected by the national researchers (WP2) and further developed in a standardised format adapted to the use in the Open Studio. This was fully the case for OS1 and OS2, while for OS3 (green commons) and OS4 (masculinity roles), it was necessary to make an additional search to have a sufficiently balanced portfolio. All the better stories used are available on the RESISTIRÉ project [website](#).

The ORU team in charge of analysing the narratives (WP4) was briefed on the OS method and process, as well as the personas. This allowed ORU to identify narratives that could be inspiring for the development of the personas. Personas were developed by the YW team in steps: firstly, defining a template and pilot persona to be validated by the team (YW, ORU and SU). Secondly, defining the basic characteristics of 6-7 personas for each OS, checking the consistency and the coverage of inequalities. Thirdly, the development of first drafts for each set of personas (one for each OS), including the choice of visuals and the development of quotes (inspired from the real quotes in the narratives). These drafts were reviewed by the team before their finalisation. All the personas are available on the RESISTIRÉ project [website](#).

Finally, a package of materials was prepared and sent to all the participants one week prior to each OS. This included a briefing note on the project, the OS approach and practical information, an introduction to the theme that included results from the research phase (WP2, 3 and 4), and the set of better stories.

Open Studio 1 – Better is Possible: Improving Support for Healthcare Workers

The first Open Studio of the first cycle was held on the 30th of September and the 1st of October, 2021, and was titled 'Better is Possible: Improving Support for Healthcare Workers'. It brought together a number of participants from the RESISTIRÉ consortium itself as well as experts, stakeholders, and creative people from outside of the project (see Table 1). Open Studio 1 was co-facilitated in plenary by Alain Denis (YW) and Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), with additional facilitators for work in small groups: Aart Kerremans (YW), Grace Romeo (YW), Igor Živković (YW), and Nazlı Türker (SU).

Table 1 - List of OS1 Participants

Invited Participants	Consortium Participants
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Adam Rogalewski	Alicja Bobek (TU Dublin)
Ana Vračar	Elena Ghidoni (UDEUSTO)
Clive Parkinson	Hülya Adak (SU)
Ellen Kuhlmann	Lina Sandström (ORU)
Eveline Jacobson	Lydia Gisle (Sciensano)
George Valiotis	Marina Cacace (K&I)
Niamh Humphries	Mark Ryan (TU Dublin)
Yeşim Yasin	Paloma Ellis Montalban (UDEUSTO)
	Rana Charafeddine (Sciensano)
	Tobias Axelsson (ORU)

Invited participants included a nurse, staff from a trade union and a professional association, three experts having recently published on the theme of the OS, an activist and an artist. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the plight of healthcare workers ⁴and the subpar conditions under which they work. This Open Studio sought to find solutions to the myriad difficulties faced by healthcare staff and paid special attention to the gendered dimensions of the problems faced by the healthcare sector.

One of the core issues that constituted the main focus of the Open Studio was the severe impact of the pandemic on healthcare workers' physical and mental health: they were disproportionately more likely to get ill, they suffered a range of physical conditions due to the heavy workload, and they often experienced anxiety, stress and depression. Apart from this, the pandemic emphasised the bad working conditions for healthcare workers in a lot of countries, with frequent shortages of medical personnel, equipment and other resources. Low pay and infrequent holidays, as well as the low valuation in general of a significant share of healthcare jobs are bad for working conditions and morale. Decision-making processes are often skewed as well, with healthcare management dominated by men while most healthcare workers, especially those on the frontlines against COVID-19, are women. Female healthcare workers also have to deal with patriarchal gender norms ('women are seen as carers, while men are curers') and face harassment from their patients, clients and even co-workers. The emergence of healthcare workers as a new vulnerable group was a conclusion of the expert workshop organised in June on "access the health care".

The main questions that this OS tried to find answers to were the following: how do we support healthcare workers to decrease/eliminate health impacts of the crisis? How do we respond to their needs? How can we make jobs in the healthcare sector more attractive to ensure there is enough personnel? How do we ensure fair representation for women in decision-making bodies and processes? How do we confront patriarchal norms and underlying assumptions

⁴ A broad definition of healthcare workers was used, including all lines of care as well as informal care and care for elderly.

about female healthcare workers? To these and related questions, the Open Studio was meant to provide a multitude of responses and potential solutions.

References

- Duijs, S. E., Haremaker, A., Bourik, Z., Abma, T. A. & Verdonk, P. (2021). Pushed to the Margins and Stretched to the Limit: Experiences of Freelance Eldercare Workers During the Covid-19 Pandemic in the Netherlands. *Feminist Economics*, 27(1-2), 217-235.
- Hankivsky, O., Grace, D., Hunting, G. et al. (2014). An intersectionality-based policy analysis framework: critical reflections on a methodology for advancing equity. *Int J Equity Health* 13, 119.
- Female Healthcare Professionals During the Pandemic in the Gender Perspective / http://www.temizgiysi.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Ne_Minnet_Ne_Siddet_ENG.pdf
- Heřmanová, M. (2020, April 9). Kdo se o nás postará? Migrantky na českém trhu práce. Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences. [Press release]. Retrieved <https://www.soc.cas.cz/aktualita/kdo-se-o-nas-postara-migrantky-na-ceskem-trhu-prace>
- Katuska, M. (2021). Pandémia bola poslednou kvapkou, zo zdravotníctva odchádzajú stovky sestier. [Pandemic Has Been the Last Straw, Hundreds of Nurses Leaving Health Services.] SME. Available at: <https://domov.sme.sk/c/22657266/slovensko-zdravotnictvo-sestry-odchody-covid-pandemia.html>
- Osservatorio Domina (2020). Il lavoro domestico e l'emergenza COVID-19 (Estratto del Rapporto annuale sul lavoro domestico 2020). Available at: <https://associazionedomina.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Dossier-12-lavoro-domestico-covid19-2020.pdf>
- Regenold, N. & Vindrola-Padros, C. (2021). Gender Matters: A Gender Analysis of Healthcare Workers' Experiences during the First COVID-19 Pandemic Peak in England. *Social Sciences* 10, 43.
- Wenham, C., Smith, J., Davies, S. E. et al. (2020). Women are most affected by pandemics – lessons from past outbreaks. *Nature* 583, 194-198.

Open Studio 2 – Better is Possible: Solutions for Inclusive Telework

The second Open Studio of the first cycle was held on the 6th and 7th of October 2021 and was titled 'Better is Possible: Solutions for Inclusive Telework'. The Open Studio was facilitated in plenary by Alain Denis (YW) and Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), with additional facilitation for work in the small groups provided by Grace Romeo (YW), Igor Živković (YW), and Nazlı Türker (SU).

Participants were from both the RESISTIRÉ consortium itself as well as experts, stakeholders, and creative people from outside of the project (see Table 2).

Table 2 - List of OS2 Participants

Invited Participants	Consortium Participants
Agnes Uhereczky	Alicja Bobek (TU Dublin)
Asli Odman	Anne Laure Humbert (OBU)
Dominika Čupková	Anne-Charlott Callerstig (ORU)
Jan Waeben	Charoula Tzanakou (OBU)
Juan Arasan	Claudia Aglietti (K&I)
Kari Hadjivassiliou	Dag Balkmar (ORU)
Klara Cozlová	Dolores Morondo (UDEUSTO)
Rossitsa Steliyanova	Federica Rosetti (Sciensano)
	Hülya Adak (SU)
	Lina Sandström (ORU)
	Mercedes Oleaga (UDEUSTO)
	Sylvia Gavigan (TU Dublin)
	Vanda Maufras Černoorská (ISAS)

Invited participants included mainly experts active in academia or as consultant (6), a staff member of an employer's association and an artist.

During the COVID-19 outbreak and associated lockdowns, most countries required work to be done remotely if possible. Although some jobs are not 'teleworkable', a lot of them are. This means that a large share of the population stopped going to the office and started to work from home. Even though the lockdowns have, by and large, come to an end, telework will likely, in some form or other, remain a permanent feature of the post-pandemic society.

Such a large shift in the organisation of work naturally comes with a whole range of consequences, both positive and negative. The main advantages are the increased flexibility, more autonomy in people's work, and the possibility of combining professional work with domestic work and/or caring responsibilities.

However, there are several negative effects and possibly exacerbated inequalities as well showing that telework could increase the labour market gap, rather than decreasing it. One of the main inequalities to consider is the increased workload on women. Working from home means that there is more work in the household to be done, and often this responsibility falls on women. This increases the workload for women, but also risks constraining women to the domestic sphere once again. After the lockdowns, women could end up teleworking more than men in order to combine their work with work in the household. As mentioned in the report on the national research work: "The national researchers are almost unanimous in pointing out that it was women who bore the brunt of the increase in unpaid care work and the decrease in employment. There has been insufficient support for reconciling the demands of care, domestic labour, and work in the light of school closures and the increase in teleworking."

Another area in which telework will have a big impact is the domain of physical and mental health. Mental health effects could include anxiety, depression, sleep disorders, low vital energy, suicidal thoughts and attempts, all of which became worse during the crisis. Physical health effects could be linked to physical pains due to ergonomic deficiencies and a lack of exercise.

Finally, the trend of increased telework is not necessarily egalitarian. People in poverty or social exclusion often face a digital gap: they either cannot afford proper equipment or don't have the skills to work with digital tools. Many professions are excluded from telework as physical presence is necessary (in factories, for essential jobs like in health care). Telework requires enough space at home to work comfortably, which is often not the case.

Therefore, the Open Studio tried to address these core issues: how do we make sure that telework does not lead to more work for women and a re-traditionalisation of gender roles? How do we prevent social isolation and encourage healthier patterns of interaction? How can we still provide safe spaces in times of remote work? What tools do we have to counteract digital inequalities? And how do we provide adequate spaces for telework?

References

- Derndorfer, J., Disslbacher, F., Lechinger, V., Mader, K., & Six, E. (2021). Home, Sweet Home? The Impact of Working from Home on the Division of Unpaid Work during the COVID-19 Lockdown. SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3831914>
- Hankivsky, O., Grace, D., Hunting, G. et al. (2014). An intersectionality-based policy analysis framework: critical reflections on a methodology for advancing equity. *Int J Equity Health* 13, 119.
- ISPETTORATO DEL LAVORO. (2020). Relazioni annuali sulle convalide delle dimissioni e risoluzioni consensuali delle lavoratrici madri e dei lavoratori padri <https://www.ispettorato.gov.it/it-it/studiestatistiche/Pagine/Relazione-annuale-sulle-convalide.aspx>
- Lambert, A. & Cayouette-Remblière, J. (Eds.). (2021). *L'explosion des inégalités - Classes, genre et générations*. Editions de l'Aube.
- Statistik Austria (2021). Arbeitsmarktstatistik, 1. Quartal 2021. Mikrozensus-Arbeitskräfteerhebung [Labour market statistics, 1st quarter 2021. Micro-census workforce survey]. http://www.statistik.at/wcm/idc/idcplg?IdcService=GET_NATIVE_FILE&RevisionSelectionMethod=LatestReleased&dDocName=126323 [accessed on 28 June 2021].
- Wenham, C., Smith, J., Davies, S. E. et al. (2020). Women are most affected by pandemics – lessons from past outbreaks. *Nature* 583, 194-198.

Open Studio 3 – Better is Possible: Solutions for Inclusive Access to Green Commons

The third Open Studio of the first cycle was held on the 12th and 13th of October, 2021, and was titled ‘Better is Possible: Solutions for Inclusive Access to Green Commons’. It brought together a number of participants from the RESISTIRÉ consortium itself as well as experts, stakeholders, and creative people from outside of the project (see Table 3). Open Studio 3 was co-facilitated by Alain Denis (YW) and Dag Balkmar (ORU), with additional facilitators for work in small groups: Anne-Charlott Callerstig (ORU), Grace Romeo (YW), Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), and Aart Kerremans (YW).

Table 3 - List of OS3 Participants

Invited Participants	Consortium Participants
Gretta Louw	Claudia Aglietti (K&I)
K. Murat Güney	Kristen Biehl (SU)
Linda Gustafsson	Lorenzo Lionello (Sciensano)
Łukasz Drózda	Mark Ryan (TU Dublin)
Margarita Triguero-Mas	Rana Charafeddine (Sciensano)
Nathan Coyle	Roberto Cibir (ISAS)
Yaşar Adanalı	Sara Clavero (TU Dublin)
	Tanya Warnaars (ESF)

Invited participants included two civil servants from municipalities involved in urban planning, an architect, two experts (researchers), two activists (from NGOs) and an artist.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the many benefits of green commons in terms of health and maintaining social connections, but it also exposed the unequal access to these kinds of spaces and the outstanding issues that are associated with them. This Open Studio sought to find solutions to the many limitations that green commons still have when various vulnerable and marginalised groups in society try to make use of them and enjoy their supposedly universal benefits.

One of the core issues that constituted the main focus of the Open Studio was the unequal availability of green spaces and the open question of how to create new green commons. The urban grey-green divide, meaning the phenomenon where lower-income neighbourhoods are less green and farther removed from urban green spaces, has severe impacts on physical and mental health inequalities, on the ability of people in different neighbourhoods to engage in social interaction and community-building, on the unequal management of green spaces, and on the design of green spaces. These situation reflects the values of dominant socioeconomic groups. Furthermore, this divide exacerbates intersectional inequalities, with

class/socioeconomic status often intersecting with ethnicity/race, nationality/migrant status, sexual orientation, gender identity, etc.

A second core issue constitutes the accessibility of green commons in terms of disability, age, and space. With regards to disability, can disabled people make their way around green spaces independently and is there adequate provision of adapted facilities? As for age, does the infrastructure of green spaces allow for visits by elderly people, teenagers and children? Finally, in terms of space, crowded spaces dominated by specific groups can exclude the presence of other groups, i.e., noisy children prevent elderly people from visiting. Another core issue encompasses the various safety concerns for green spaces: empty and secluded areas can pose safety issues for women and other groups, children playing in public spaces involves risks from traffic and dangerous people, and blue areas (bodies of water) pose an additional safety issue for children and people who are unable to swim. Lastly, the unequal management of green spaces and the often-discriminatory policing that happens in and around them have negative effects on the uptake of green spaces by marginalised groups.

The main questions that this OS tried to find answers to, were the following: how can we ensure that green spaces are available to everyone and how do we reduce the grey-green divide? How can we channel existing community impulses to create new green commons? Are there ways in which we can further stimulate local bottom-up initiatives for more green space? How do we design public green spaces so that a diverse group of people is comfortable in them and is encouraged to seek them out? What practical, environmental, and aesthetic aspects can be changed to improve diversity of turnout? How can we make green commons adaptable depending on the time of day, the needs of users, etc.? How do we ensure that public green spaces are safe for everyone and how do we prevent (gender-based) violence even at times when green spaces are sparsely populated? How can we facilitate a more equal and diverse local management of public green spaces? How do we prevent discriminatory policing by public authorities and local law enforcement? To these and related questions, the Open Studio was meant to provide a multitude of responses and potential solutions.

References

Hankivsky, O., Grace, D., Hunting, G. et al. (2014). An intersectionality-based policy analysis framework: critical reflections on a methodology for advancing equity. *Int J Equity Health* 13, 119.

Open Studio 4 – Better is Possible: Transforming Masculinity Roles

The fourth Open Studio of the first cycle was held on the 14th and 15th of October 2021 and was titled 'Better is Possible: Transforming Masculinity Roles'. The Open Studio was facilitated in plenary by Alain Denis (YW) and Dag Balkmar (ORU) with additional

facilitation for work in the small groups provided by Grace Romeo (YW), Igor Živković (YW), Nathalie Wuïame (YW) and Nazlı Türker (SU).

Participants were from both the RESISTIRÉ consortium itself as well as experts, stakeholders, and creative people from outside of the project (see Table 4).

Table 4 - List of OS4 Participants

Invited Participants	Consortium Participants
Sandy Ruxton	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc (ESF)
Linzi Ladlow	Alicja Bobek (TUD)
Sevim Sancaktar	Clare Stovell (OBU)
Ritxar Bacete	Dag Balkmar (ORU)
Tomas Gunnarsson	Elena Ghidoni (UDEUSTO)
Hande Eslen-Ziya	Federica Rossetti (Sciensano)
Ebru Nihan Celkan	Leire Gartzia (UDEUSTO)
	Maria López Belloso (UDEUSTO)
	Marina Cacace (K&I)
	Sara Clavero (TUD)
	Tobias Axelsson (ORU)
	Yvonne Galigan (TUD)

Invited participants included five expert-researchers (from academia, NGO and consultancy) and two artists.

The COVID-19 outbreak highlighted some of the gender differences that existed in society. The gender care gap and the large amounts of unpaid work that women were performing became more visible. However, at the same time, the fact that this inequality became more visible meant that men were starting to be more aware of it, and some responded by taking up more of this work.

Therefore, the pandemic has created the opportunity to rethink masculinities and male ideals. As mentioned, there has been the fact that men have increased their amount of domestic work during the pandemic (even though the burden still disproportionately fell on women). Another opportunity is the increased involvement of fathers in childcare activities. Research has shown that fathers have become more involved with their children. One consequence of the pandemic that could enforce this trend is teleworking. As many people were forced to work from home during the pandemic, they were suddenly spending more time in the household, and with their families. For men, this was even more unusual, as in practice they are often not allowed to take up paternity leave or ask for a flexible schedule to be able to do care activities.

Finally, during the pandemic, fathers have also been disadvantaged by societies' views on men and care. They were often not allowed to be present during the birth of their child, and it was difficult for single parents to take care of their child due to traveling restrictions.

Therefore, the questions that the Open Studio tries to address are the following: Can we use the momentum created by a revision of traditional work arrangements to contribute to the development or reinforcement of caring masculinities? Can these changes lead to a shift in the organisational culture and image of the ideal (male) worker and men's identity? How do we design policies that support men in taking family responsibilities? How do we ensure that fathers can maintain contact with their child? And how to allow fathers to fully participate in the birth of their child in all circumstances?

References

- Cook, R (2020), Covid should make fathers rethink how and when they work -and employer can help, Kings College of London, News Centre, <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/news/covid-should-make-fathers-rethink-how-and-when-they-work-and-employers-can-help>.
- Craig, L., Churchill, B. (2021), Dual-earner parent couples' work and care during COVID-19, Elliott, K. (2015). Caring Masculinities. *Men and Masculinities*, 19(3), 240–259. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109718415576203>
- Hanlon, N. (2012). *Masculinities, care and equality: Identity and nurture in Men's Lives*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Gender Work and Organisation, Supplement: Feminist Frontiers, Volume 28, Issue S 1, January 2021.
- Hankivsky, O., Grace, D., Hunting, G. et al. (2014). An intersectionality-based policy analysis framework: critical reflections on a methodology for advancing equity. *Int J Equity Health* 13, 119.
- Ruppner, L., Tan, X., Scarborough, W., Landivar, L. C., & Collins, C. (2021). Shifting Inequalities? Parents' Sleep, Anxiety, and Calm during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Australia and the United States. *Men and Masculinities*, 24(1), 181–188. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1097184X21990737>.
- Kreyenfeld, M and Zinn, S, Coronavirus and care: How the coronavirus crisis affected fathers' involvement in Germany, *Demographic research*, Volume 44, article 4, pg 99-124 <https://www.demographic-research.org/Volumes/Vol44/4/> DOI: 10.4054/DemRes.2021.44.4.
- Wojnicka, K. (2021), Men and masculinities in time of crisis: between care and protection, *NORMA*, 16:1, 1.5.

Ideas for actions

This section includes descriptions of action-ideas developed in the Open Studios that will be used as input to:

- Formulate recommendations towards different target groups including policymakers, civil society organisations (including NGOs), employers, and other kinds of stakeholders.
- Launch pilot actions that will test and demonstrate the potential of innovative approaches.
- Feed the research agenda of RESISTIRÉ (the second cycle of research activities) and beyond.

As mentioned in the introduction above, the action-ideas are descriptions of the actions as they came out of the Open Studios, without any check for feasibility or improvements by the editors. Even if the authors tried to have some consistency in their presentation, this was not always possible based on the output from the Open Studio. Some of the action-ideas described have the potential to inspire more than one of the outputs mentioned above: potential pilot actions could e.g. be recommendations and vice-versa. The authors have decided to allocate the action-ideas into one of the sections below, without repeating the same content in another section. The table below gives an overview of all action-ideas and for which type of output they can be used as well as the section where it is described.

Table: list of Action-ideas by type of output.

☑ = described in this section ☐ = also valid for this type of output

	Operational recommendations	Pilot action	Research Agenda
Developing holistic care for healthcare workers (Action 1.1)		☑	
Equality and diversity policy plan for hospitals (Action 1.2)	☑		
Ask healthcare workers what will help them and make the profession more attractive (Action 1.3)		☑	☐
Reducing the burden on frontline workers by delegating non-medical tasks (Action 1.4)	☐	☑	
Giving a voice to the migrant workforce in care with an irregular work status (Action 1.5)		☑	
Role to be played by municipalities in developing holistic care for healthcare workers (Action 1.6)	☑	☐	
Creating a platform to exchange goods/services to alleviate the needs of staff in the care sector (Action 1.7)		☑	
The right to telework (Action 2.1)	☑		
Inclusive digital leadership (Action 2.2)		☑	
Work-life balance and care (Action 2.3)	☑		

	Operational recommendations	Pilot action	Research Agenda
Urban planning (Action 2.4)			☑
A caring workspace (Action 2.5)	☑	☑	☑
Platform for digital training and inspiration (Action 2.6)		☑	
The right to disconnect (Action 2.7)	☑		
Toolkit for bottom-up initiatives (Action 3.1)		☑	
Develop citizen initiatives to transform unused public space into new green space (Action 3.2)	☑	☑	
Programming the use of green space (Action 3.3)		☑	
Green spaces as eco-systems of care (Action 3.4)		☑	☑
The importance of greenery and green interventions (Action 3.5)	☑	☑	☑
Gender equality policy (Action 3.6)		☑	
How to mitigate gentrification (Action 3.7)	☑	☑	☑
Promotion of caring workplaces (Action 4.1)		☑	
Policy shifting norms (Action 4.2)	☑		
Concrete care (Action 4.3)	☑	☑	
Leadership / mentoring program (Action 4.4)	☑	☑	
Employer recommendations to improve employee wellbeing (Action 4.5)	☑		
Education platform on COVID-19: care and gender roles (Action 4.6)		☑	

Operational recommendations

The action-ideas described in this section will serve as input for the development of operational recommendations for different stakeholders: policymakers at different levels (national, regional, local), CSOs and NGOs, employers and employers' associations, and others. These recommendations will be developed in the form of guidelines and in the description of promising practices. They will include advice on how to avoid increases (and bring about decreases) in various inequalities. Some of the action-ideas described were sometimes meant to become a pilot action. If mentioned in this section, it is because the team judged they had the potential to be used as inspiration for the formulation of operational recommendations was higher than their potential as a pilot action.

Equality and diversity policy plan for hospitals⁵ (Action 1.2)

Impacts Pursued

- Diversity and equality in the workplace
- Encourage proper training (and accountability) of management
- Address and eliminate harassment issues
- Raise the standards for professional practices

Action Description

A two-part, bottom-up approach that identifies and addresses specific structural flaws that are increasing inequalities in health institutions.

Part 01 - Develop a template / strategy for structure that addresses the most important issues facing healthcare workers today:

- Participatory development to identify needs 'on the ground'
- Informed by the needs of various professional positions, levels and focuses – not only nurses, but also doctors, management, maintenance, etc.
- Asking critical questions, like 'what barriers exist (particularly in nursing) that de-incentivise women to move up in the hierarchy?'
- 'System benchmark' – what systems are already in place with similar objectives? How can we learn from these / what can be improved?

Part 02 – The implementation of this strategy into hospitals / institutions:

- An iterative process – implementation followed by monitoring in order to identify shortcomings and revise the strategy where necessary. This would include external monitoring, but would also require additional training for managers so that they can hold themselves and their staff accountable. Critical reviews should not only look at quantifiable data, but should also investigate qualitative factors like process, atmosphere, culture, etc. to avoid this structure becoming a 'symbolic action'
- Evolving strategy / procedures would then be shared to produce / improve other pilots elsewhere

Scalability

- As time may be limited for all of these actions, Part 01 and Part 02 could be two separate actions, the first addressed in cycle one and the second in cycle two. The first action (or step) could be envisaged as a pilot action rather than a guideline or recommendation.

⁵ Actions are numbered based on the output of the Open Studios to make the link with the individual OS reports.

- This is a bottom-up approach, meaning we start local, with individual institution(s). If the project gains momentum and is introduced elsewhere, the goal would be for it to inspire top-down regulation / accreditation.

Promotion – How to ‘sell’ the plan?

- Gender PLUS – Focuses on gender but does not exclude other inequalities / does include intersections.
- Hospitals are currently experiencing shortages - if they are perceived as a good place of work, they will attract more people and retain current personnel.

Target groups

Beneficiaries: All healthcare workers at different levels, including support staff in hospitals.

Primary: Management of hospitals

Secondary: Policy-makers (at national level)

Role to be played by municipalities in developing holistic care for healthcare workers (Action 1.6)

Impacts pursued:

- Provide free/affordable childcare
 - Community-building & solidarity
 - Increase in participation to art
 - Mental health of children improved
 - Creative and emotional intelligence developed in children
 - Create space for different languages to be shared/learned (linguistic diversity)
- Working against hierarchies by bringing the children together (migrant, janitor, surgeon...) - having open the program to healthcare workers’ children and reducing inequities and supporting their relationship
- Bringing childcare and community building together
 - Community building & sense of solidarity improved
 - Alleviate pressure on health workers by providing care services in the community
 - wellbeing of parents/healthcare workers improved
 - Bridging generations by connecting elderly and children (elderly home & kindergartens)
- Prestige of municipalities increased in the eyes of 'voters'

Action description

Child-oriented programs run by municipalities which are open to children of all healthcare workers (everyone involved in the health ecosystem). The program is developed and run-in cooperation with people from arts and culture sector, NGOs working with children, NGOs working on ecology, different municipality units. Public libraries, theatres, dance venues, galleries and art schools and municipal buildings are used as venues

while storytelling, singing / music, open air activities at the nature are composed the main elements of the programs. Gender+ and diversity perspective are added to every activity. At the end of the program, 21st century fairy stories, songs & art work are devised with and by children with gender+ and diversity perspective and they can be exhibited in public spaces (murals etc.).

Details of the program/activities:

- Taking children to parks and woods, connecting with trees (storytelling, art, walking, plays)
- Ensuring the integration of children of migrants
- Creating multilingual programs
- Making use of existing resources of municipality (experts, spaces, etc.)
- Also contributing to the arts & culture sector (by paying them for their time and space) that has suffered from the pandemic

Budget of the program:

If there is a program fee, it should be an income-based contribution which is affordable and even free for some. Municipalities can also afford such programmes by covering the fees of participants. Trainers can be selected from municipality certified preschool educators & collaborating institutions (see above) and volunteers. To reach out and mobilise the volunteers, municipalities can run a platform to connect people who are willing to take part in childcare (a platform like Back up Nurses). Companies can donate food and/or volunteers can cook food on the spot. Existing programs for supporting local farmers can be integrated to the model in ensuring meals supply.

The results would be used for different purposes:

- The model is likely to be an effective example in social policy area which can be promoted in political campaigns by local governments.
- The model can be easily replicated by other municipalities with the participation of children from different socio-economic background once the pilot action runs successfully.
- There could be models where volunteers (from different ages) could be used (especially in activities that aim to raise ecological consciousness)

Target groups

Primary: everyone involved in the health ecosystem and their children.

Other stakeholders: the arts and culture sector, NGOs working with children, NGOs working on ecology, NGOs working on gender equality, municipalities, kindergartens, and elderly homes.

The right to telework (work-life balance) (Action 2.1)

Background and justification

This action was originally labelled as “Telework ability of not tele workable jobs” but was changed at the end of the discussion.

The original theme was chosen as many professions lose on the potential benefits of telework, because their jobs are considered to be done physically. But, for many of these jobs, when you start splitting the job into tasks, you can identify tasks that can be done through telework. The amenability to telework was brought in as a concept and the fact that studies exist classifying professions and jobs on a scale.

The overall objective is to create more equality, making sure that all would get the opportunity to telework if this is possible. This is considered to benefit more women based on statistics of women working in sectors that are amenable to telework.

The prejudices that exist at management level in many organizations was considered as a main barrier, and as a source of creation of inequality. The type of “mentality” that leads to such behaviour and management style (e.g., control against trust) is at the root cause and is often also linked to a lack of attention to the well-being of the workforce.

Impacts pursued

- To position telework as a right for the employee, but a right that always has to be applied on a voluntary base, never to be imposed (directly or indirectly, through the recognition of the right to rearrangement of working time for personal / family needs).
- To fight the prejudices against telework that exist among management of organizations
- To promote the amenability concept and the openness to allow for tasks to be eligible for telework.

This right being voluntary should help to avoid that telework would lead to increased inequalities. Still, the risk exists that adverse effects of telework would dominate against the benefits. The potentially negative effects of telework therefore have to be taken up: risks like performing longer hours, slower career progression due to loss of personal contacts, impact on physical and mental health,

Action description

Targeting employers:

The proposed action is to create a guideline in which:

- The business case for the employer is explained. Although the arguments are many and already known (attracting talent, better WLB and therefore motivation of staff, lower carbon footprint,), this remains a leverage and a way to convince managers who are still afraid of telework
- Include also in these guidelines information on the potential risks in terms of physical and mental health and how to prevent these risks

- Provide information on the responsibility of the employer based on today's legislation, more concretely that the rules on safety and health at work are applicable in the case of telework.
- Provide information on good practices with regard to the sharing of the costs this implies for the employee.

These guidelines for employers would be accompanied by recommendations targeting the national policy level and the trade unions with following objectives:

- Make them aware of the need for equal access to telework, and that the way to achieve this is through collective bargaining and the establishment of clear rules for access to telework.
- Make them aware of the need to enforce the current occupational and safety and health at work (European) legislation making the employers liable for the consequences of telework.
- Identify and explain the existing laws at national level that can be considered as inspiring practice for other countries, many of these laws being very recent and not necessarily already enforced (France, Spain, Belgium, ...)

Target groups

This action addresses:

- Employers (both private and public sector)
- Their associations
- Trade Unions
- National and regional authorities responsible for occupational safety and health at work

Work-life balance and care (Action 2.3)

Background and justification

Telework has the potential to improve the work-life balance mainly through the commuting time saved and the fact of working from home allowing multi-tasking between professional and private activities. When telework is combined with flexibility, the positive impact can be high.

But there are also risks associated. There is evidence that telework leads too often to longer working days. One particular way in which this is true is related to the topic of care. The home is a place where many people have caring responsibilities, for example take care of children, elderly people, people with disability. In practice, this care work falls disproportionately on women.

Teleworking could have negative impacts on women because it would force them to combine their professional work with care work, which would lead to more work overall. It could also mean that women will take up telework more often, because they are expected or even forced

to make use of teleworking to combine care work with professional work. This spoke to many of the participant's personal experiences.

Impacts pursued

- Prevent growing indirect discrimination and prevent the 'going back' in time in terms of equality, i.e., make sure women are not pressured to work from home to take care of the care responsibilities. Pressure could come from within the family and from employers. This would create a new labour market inequality.
- Make sure teleworking and care are a free choice and that women are not forced to do more domestic work.

Action description

The main focus of this action is a policy recommendation. This would include the following:

- Governments should provide free and accessible public child-care facilities
- Every household should have a nearby facility available to them. This reduces the burden on women, who are often the ones picking up the children.
- In particular, childcare facilities for children under 3 years old should be widely available. This would also reduce the stigma on women not able to take full caring responsibilities for their child in the first 3 years.
- Paternity leave should be as long as maternity leave, and compulsory and untransferable. This would not only give options to fathers on paper, but also in practice, whereas now fathers often cannot take up their full paternity leave. This policy would directly undermine cultural assumptions and customs about women being the primary responsible ones for children.
- Teleworkers should be explicitly addressed in collective bargaining agreements. Businesses should also be required to put teleworkers in their equality and work-life balance plans.

Target groups

This action addresses:

- Governments
- Businesses
- Trade unions

The right to disconnect (Action 2.7)

Background and justification

Telework has the potential to improve the work-life balance mainly through the commuting time saved and the fact of working from home allowing multi-tasking between professional and private activities. When telework is combined with flexibility, the positive impact can be high.

But there are also risks associated. There is evidence that telework leads too often to longer working days. The unclear borderline between work time and private time can lead to more stress and impacts on the mental health. Consequently, there is a need to rethink the work-life boundary management and look at issues like:

- The autonomy paradox
- The awareness of different actors on the need to take care of work-life balance (WLB) in these new circumstances (employees themselves, line managers, management, HR)
- Define the optimal level of telework in terms of productivity
- Working by objectives
- The infringement of work in the private life

Some organisations, whether public or private, have launched initiatives to protect employees from potential negative effects by blocking mail circulation in certain periods (evening – night and weekend) or by explicitly advocating the right to disconnect.

Few countries have developed legislation on this “right to disconnect”.

Impacts pursued

- To promote the concept of “the right to disconnect” to ensure telework does not have adverse effects on WLB, mental health.
- To ensure vulnerable groups, who might have to disconnect, are not discriminated at their workplace.

Action description

Targeting employers (all types of organisations, public and private, large and small):

The central idea is to develop a code of conduct for organisations that ensures the right to disconnect is applied. This code of conduct can include examples of organisations that applied such code.

The actual development of the code can be based on a benchmark

The proposed action is to create a guideline in which:

- The business case for the employer applying the right to disconnect is explained.
- Provide information on the responsibility of the employer based on today’s legislation on the right to disconnect.
- Include recommendations on how to integrate the right to disconnect in the company culture.

Targeting the business schools and teachers in secondary education in charge of teaching societal subjects:

- Make them aware of the concept of the right to disconnect and its importance.
- Provide adapted material that could be used in the teaching curriculum.

Target groups

This action addresses:

- Employers (both private and public sector)

- Their associations
- Trade Unions: to strengthen their role in assuring the respect of the right to disconnect laws implementation.
- Business schools and secondary education

How to mitigate gentrification (Action 3.7)

Background and justification

One of the consequences of creating more green public space and the increased attractiveness of the neighbourhood where this takes place, is the risk this leads to gentrification.

The original intention of this action line was to avoid gentrification, but it was decided in the course of the discussion to change this in mitigating gentrification, as avoiding is probably not a realistic objective.

Impacts pursued

- Mitigate the process of gentrification.
- Ensure the use of the green space in the neighbourhood by all the different target groups present.
- Change the discourse around greening (going away from greening having an economic value and going back to greening having a value per se/per health/per the society)
- Create equal access to green spaces, also in grey zones.

Action description

Two different action lines were identified:

- Radical innovation
- Making recommendations to put different policies together to have a higher impact

The radical innovation proposed would be to create a cooperative of actors around a newly created green space. This cooperative would federate all the users and stakeholders, local business, authorities, individuals, associations, ..., and would act as an economic player. Federating users and owners of real estate, it would play a role on the real estate market: buying and selling properties.

The second action would be to develop guidelines on how to mitigate gentrification when investing in a new or upgraded green space. The key point of these guidelines is the need for a holistic approach and to ensure that actions from different policy domains are being combined.

This would include based on the input of the discussion (ideas and points that partly overlap):

- Combine greening with social policies, e.g., with the development of affordable housing in the area as a method to directly protect areas from gentrification.

- Apply new policies such as rent control and rent freezing
- Using users' participation to define the new green space; making it less attractive for gentrification
- Integrate social related projects into the green space; using the programming of the use (see action-idea 3.3 and 3.4 below in the section “pilot projects”) to be attractive to the local population but less to attract new groups.
- Leveraging on green spaces as a space of mobilization, community feeling (fighting gentrification).
- The role the city can play as landowner, particularly to use other criteria than added value or profit when selling land or property
- The use of concession by the authorities to ensure quality and affordability of services, rather than profit maximisation.

Target groups

Municipalities.

The stakeholders in neighbourhoods that are investing in new green spaces: (potential) users of the green spaces, those living in the area, the businesses and other organisations having activities in the neighbourhood.

Policy shifting norms (Action 4.2)

Background and justification

Based on the many ideas to make policy recommendations expressed during the first day of the Open Studio on “Transforming masculinity roles”, a cluster of ideas was created to look at how to influence the higher levels of policies and how to ‘shift the norms’ to embed the value of care into policies.

All these reflections started from a strong sense of doing things differently and the rediscovered practice of looking out for others due to COVID-19, as well as the need to address the higher-level norms, as care is everyone’s responsibility.

A provocative and radical example given was to propose a new article to the EU treaty. More generally, ideas were linked to mainstreaming care which would also make it easier to ‘gender-proof’ the policies.

Impacts pursued

- The overall goal is to improve individual well-being
- To promote a holistic view on care
- To encourage more involvement across the spectrum of all forms of care
- The creation of caring structures and mechanisms
- Base policies on intersectional equality as well as means-tested policies

Action description

Recommendations were formulated at different levels and for different target groups.

(1)

A first level is addressing the national authorities, but is actually targeting the employers. The central idea is to shift from “**employee rights**” to “**employer obligations**”. An example is the right to request flexible work. The problem is that both parties, employer and employee, still have to agree. The employer has no obligation to accept a request and grant a form of flexibility. In the process of making a recommendation, two actions would be needed:

- Include gender experts in the process
- Make a stakeholder mapping of those who would benefit from this change (clients, suppliers, society at large, ...) to strengthen the argumentation

(2)

The second level relates to the need to invest more in the **social infrastructure** as part of the recovery process. This is necessary to strengthen the system and its resilience to handle care needs. The EU advocates investing part of the national recovery plan funding into the green deal and in digitalisation, but COVID-19 has shown that the same need exists for the social infrastructure (as opposed to the physical infrastructure). This action line could be made concrete through the development of a MANIFESTO, underlying the responsibility of the EU and the Member States to invest according to their financial capacity. Examples of the more advanced countries could be given, making the parallel with their better performance in terms of fighting the pandemic.

A more radical approach to a manifesto could be to propose a new article for the EU treaty formulated in a universal way, putting the right to care at the highest juridical level.

(3)

A third level of action is inspired by the role played by **mutual aid organisations** during the lockdowns and after. The recommendations are rather practical and addressing national and regional authorities. The content should include:

- The need to recognise the role they play in the care system and the fact that they fill a care gap that is not covered by the formal care system, whether by the private sector or the public sector
- The fact that the care system can learn from the experiences of these actors. They are in direct contact with vulnerable groups who are often below the radar of the formal system. They can act as an early warning system to detect unmet care needs in society.
- The need to integrate these organisations into the care system, making sure the other care actors can support them and vice versa.

Target groups

Apart from the national authorities which are the prime target for the recommendations formulated, the following target groups were also identified, often because they could act as allies in making the recommendations known:

- Employers, trade unions
- Feminist lobby groups
- Organisations providing care services
- Civil society organisations
- Municipalities
- Young people, universities, students
- Education institutions at all levels (to reach young people)
- National healthcare and the care sector in general
- Career guidance organisations
- Family associations
- Policymakers linked to job-creation
- Design organisations
- Environmental protection organisations

Employer recommendations to improve employee wellbeing (Action 4.5)

Background and Justification

In earlier sessions, the group concluded that employers were largely absent from the better stories. Organisations, therefore, have an opportunity to assert their responsibility for promoting a healthy work-life balance by acknowledging the roles and responsibilities of employees outside of the workplace.

This action involves various recommendations to improve employee wellbeing through the promotion of equal domestic/care obligations. In this action, 'care' is a broad term that goes beyond child care and care for dependent others, to include forms of care which are not typically addressed, including self-care. By expanding the notion of care, the intention is to acknowledge single employees with no dependents who are forced to accommodate the obligations of fellow employees and the resulting workload.

Impacts Pursued (can also be considered selling points for organisations to implement these recommendations)

- Better WLB to increase employee wellbeing (and productivity)
- Considering WLB beyond childcare
- Building employee loyalty/commitment to the organisation
- Contributing to an innovative culture and increasing competitiveness in the market

- Attracting and retaining ‘talent’/employees
- Preventing burn-out

Action Description

This initiative involves recommendations for both immediate and long-term impacts on employee wellbeing. Several recommendations have already been identified:

- Providing more comprehensive care leave, along with efforts to destigmatise/encourage the use of that care leave
- Proactively distinguishing and promoting WLB benefits to current employees as well as potential new hires by listing types of flexible work available in job adverts
- Addressing daily/urgent aspects of care that extra (care) days wouldn't necessarily cover by fostering agility for the employee, but within certain boundaries to prevent exploitation. One example given was flexible hours – if an organization is operational between 8:00-18:00, the employee is free to select their active hours, increasing their daily flexibility. However, mechanisms should be put in place to discourage employees from working extra hours where possible.
- Valorising personal development by incentivising employees through annual reviews, appraisals, promotions, etc.
- Including conversations with all employees about care needs in annual reviews and recruitment (assume a broad understanding of care)
- Acknowledging the right to disconnect/the need to diversify tasks, for example by limiting amount of time spent per week on Zoom
- Promoting healthy work culture and relationships by maintaining employee connection /in-person interactions

To identify additional recommendations and develop a holistic strategy, the group recommended the following efforts and considerations for further development:

- **Benchmarking:** Mapping of good practices to build on innovative flexible working practices developed by women (especially in male-dominated industries) and promoting them to men
- **Considering policy vs. practice:** Ensuring barriers/demotivating factors for sharing care for women are addressed (e.g., transfer mechanisms). Women often lead work-family decision making.
- **Modular recommendations:** Fitting the size and structure of companies for greatest impact, or alternatively a training of how to develop/adapt the general recommendations based on scheme.

Target groups

Policy for equal office/HR, trade unions, professional organisations, managers

Prototyping and scalability

To promote these recommendations, small-scale prototypes of 'progressive work models' could be implemented to test impact on health and productivity. Insights could inform qualitative research efforts in this area, for example: Will the wellbeing of employees (more flexibility and care) lead to more productivity and increased performance of the company?

Pilot projects

This section includes descriptions of action-ideas that constitute the long list of potential ideas for pilot actions. These actions will be screened and characterised further in a next task of RESISTIRÉ (6.2) and at least two actions will be selected for implementation. In this process, some actions might be merged and/or transformed to make them feasible for implementation in the context of the project. More concretely, positively evaluated ideas for pilot projects will be developed further, after which a call will be launched for interested organisations to implement the selected actions. More than two actions can be selected if this is feasible with the resources available.

As mentioned in the introduction above, the action-ideas described in this section are descriptions of the actions as they came out of the Open Studios, without any check for feasibility or improvements by the editors. Even if the authors tried to have some consistency in their presentation, this was not always possible based on the output from the Open Studio. Some of the action-ideas described could serve to inspire the development of operational recommendations but are mentioned in this section because the team judged they had the highest potential as a potential pilot action.

Developing holistic care for healthcare workers (Action 1.1)

Impacts pursued

- Create a culture of collective wellbeing and healing
- Develop resilience and incite creativity towards personal and collective healing for healthcare workers
- Contribute to the mental health of healthcare workers through collective and creative engagements with others who share similar challenges

Action description

6 month/one-year program developed to increase the well-being of hospital workers. Ideally, it is based on the one-health approach (human health, animal health, environmental health, all integrated, etc.) and focuses on well-being instead of care. Therefore, it prioritises mental health with the integration of art and creative practices such as collective nature walks and other physical and contemplative activities offered physically and/or online (e.g., yoga, qi gong, tai chi, meditation, etc.), storytelling, and art sessions (online or physical), local and

online sharing circles for people sharing similar challenges and interests (also benefit the patients).

The program ideally aims to support hospital workers in connecting with, processing & sharing difficult emotions (e.g., death, grief, loss, despair, hopelessness) that are faced every day at the hospitals.

Designated person from each hospital can encourage and coordinate workers to participate in the program. Institutional encouragement and recognition are the key for the success of the program. Encouragement can be in the form of extra time off or bonuses for the workers and tax-advantageous and/or certification for the hospitals with the supervision of Ministry of Health.

The program will also help create a sense of community and collegiality (across hierarchical and other divisions) among hospital workers, as they will be coming together with different people across the care spectrum (from cleaners to cooks to nurses to doctors), fostering a sense of collective resilience in the face of shared vulnerabilities and challenges.

The program can be developed by/in cooperation with mentor organisation(s) like:

- Line Arts (Manchester)
- Transformative Activism (SU Gender)
- Other Healing Justice / Healing Solidarity initiatives

Next step: To develop a "holistic care strategy" for hospitals (supporting the mental health and wellbeing of staff (time off, resources...) and integrate childcare programs for children of healthcare workers in the long run.

Target groups

Primary: hospital workers

Secondary: families/relatives of hospital workers and patients

Other stakeholders: psychology units of hospitals, the arts and culture sector, and the Ministry of Health

Ask healthcare workers what will help them and make the profession more attractive (Action 1.3)

Impacts pursued

- Empower healthcare workers
 - Boost their morale
 - Make the activists feel stronger
 - Improve their role and place in decision-making

- Contribute to the agenda setting (at policy level)
- Fight the status-quo (between the different professions)

Action description

Perform qualitative research in the form of participatory workshops.

This would be done with health care workers with a migration background. Their needs and ideas should be similar to those of mainstream groups, and have the advantage to allow to understand also their specific situation.

- How many workshops? in how many countries?
- Working with a heterogeneous group or homogeneous?

The results would be used for different purposes:

- For impact on policy-making: as input in a roundtable discussion with decision-makers. This roundtable should lead to recommendations and/or agenda setting
- For empowering the healthcare workers themselves:
 - Stimulating the creation of concrete actions coming out of the workshops like self-help groups, online moderated platforms, ...
 - Feeding results on various communication channels including online media to get into a conversation and inspire activists.

The setting-up of the research should be done with the buy-in of professional associations. Not to involve them in the research itself (except the roundtable), but more on the research design and potentially also assistance in recruitment of participants.

Target groups

Primary: all healthcare workers at different levels, including support staff in hospitals.

Not clear if the action would involve health care at home and non-formal employment.

Secondary: Management of hospitals, professional associations (and unions?), and policymakers (at national level).

Reducing the burden on frontline workers by delegating non-medical tasks and reducing the amount of necessary work (Action 1.4)

Background and justification

During the pandemic, healthcare personnel was often confronted (and still is) with work that is not part of their core tasks, i.e., caring for patients. This included such jobs as taking care of administrative tasks and paperwork, as well as communicating with relatives of patients. It might be feasible to delegate this work onto other (trained) personnel and, thus, leave the healthcare workers free to focus on their most important duties.

Impacts pursued

- Relieve the administrative burden on healthcare workers (those directly caring for patients) and have them focus on the actual care work instead
- Improve patient care
- Simplify and streamline the administrative system (country-specific)
- Provide more effective & efficient ways of interacting with patients' relatives

Action description

A potential pilot action could implement various ways of reducing the existing burdens on healthcare workers and should not just be limited to one fix. A potential solution is delegating the numerous administrative tasks that come with patient care. New administrative positions could be created and filled to help with scheduling procedures, to keep a central overview of patients and all related procedures/documentation, and to standardise ways of referring patients. Moving patients from one hospital to another also requires a lot of documentation which can be processed by administrative assistants and secretaries. In some countries, cleaning of rooms is a responsibility of nurses as well, which can be delegated to sanitation staff.

During the pandemic, a switch was made in Swedish hospitals from administration on computers to administration on paper that followed the patient around, something that was faster, required less effort, and allowed doctors and nurses to quickly get a reminder of the details of the patient's case. Typing everything into a computer and, subsequently, having to consult it for relevant information turned out to be less efficient and quick in a high-pressure environment. However, it is also safer for staff to have a centralised record of everything that's happened on a computer and which can protect them from legal consequences. In this regard, a lot of counties/hospitals in Sweden have their own administrative platforms, so it would be very helpful for them to be a (national) central platform which can easily accommodate for, i.e., patients moving from one hospital to another.

As described in the 'background' section above, the system that was implemented during COVID-19 in (some) Swedish hospitals where interns communicate with relatives could be replicated in other countries and contexts. It can also be simplified by limiting interactions to one relative per patient, so that medical staff can provide all relevant information to this contact person and, as a result, do not have to answer the same questions from multiple relatives over and over again.

For all these tasks, however, a degree of flexibility on the part of healthcare personnel should be taken into account: in certain situations, it is sometimes preferable and safer for more experienced people to carry out a task. For example, comforting a relative should only be attempted by people with the emotional support skills and capabilities to do so.

Target groups

Primary: healthcare workers taking care of patients.
Secondary: management of healthcare institutions.

Next steps

It is imperative that a few key questions are answered (before or during a potential pilot project). How does delegation of tasks impact patient care? In theory, freeing up medical personnel's time should lead to better care, but is this the case in practice? Where can we get the resources needed for additional (administrative) staff? What administrative work can simply be cut, due to being unnecessary or double work?

Potential organisations to be addressed in developing such a pilot action could include (university) hospitals or even private practices.

Giving a voice to the migrant workforce in care with an irregular work status (Action 1.5)

Background and justification

Families are in many EU countries employing migrant persons to take care of either their children or elderly parents. The pandemic and the lockdowns have shown how vulnerable these women are due to lack of integration, knowledge of the country and social networks. Apart from short-term consequences (like losing their employment during the lockdown), some structural problems also appeared. These persons often did not know they were entitled to free vaccination and/or were afraid of being vaccinated as their illegal (employment) status might be discovered.

This action is inspired by self-help initiatives that were launched by such workers during the pandemic to help each other, trying to create more permanent structures to reach this specific target group.

Impacts pursued

- Help the irregular workers get organised
- Improve the access to services to which these workers are entitled and avoid situations as we have known them during the pandemic

Action Description:

The central insight that triggers this action is the **use of employers** to reach the target group. The hypothesis is that a significant number of the families employing women irregularly for care will be willing to help their irregular employees.

One example of how they could help is simply by passing on information that can be helpful to the employee and their families. For example, the right to free vaccination.

Families/employers who are aware of how their employees could get free vaccination can pass this information to them. They can also provide the context and reassure them in terms of safety and practical steps to be undertaken. As these families / employers are strategically placed to deliver information, it's just a matter of delivering information to the employer.

Covid-19 is therefore a leverage to create a network of such families who would become a channel to pass on information to their employees. Some quotes from the participants:

- "Organise the employers who do feel responsible"
- "Employers are conveniently placed and readily connected to the sources of information"

Figure 2: extract from the Miro board

The second level is to use this network to **propose trainings** that can help the employees to prepare the next step in their career and/or their integration in the country. This can be through, e.g., language courses, computer literacy courses, ... Bringing these women together in training sessions will not only build their skills, but will also help them to increase their social network. These trainings could be organised by NGOs that offer additional services: they ideally have counselling services, trust persons in case of abuse, legal advice, etc.

Figure 3: extract from the Miro board illustrating the steps of the pilot action

The third level would be to create an exchange platform, which could even be a Facebook group, to connect these women at the local level, but also across borders.

Scalability

This idea can be implemented at a local level in one or two cities as part of RESISTIRÉ. The scalability would be to demonstrate the impact to NGOs and municipalities in other countries for them to launch similar actions.

Promotion – How to ‘sell’ the plan?

A weak point of this idea is how to reach the families? The difficulty to reach the irregular care workers is replaced by the need to reach the families employing them, which might potentially be as difficult?

Target groups

Beneficiaries: women working as caregivers with irregular employment contracts.

Direct target group: the families employing these women.

Potential project owners: NGOs who do have an offer of services for vulnerable women in place, but who as of today did not manage to reach this specific target group of irregularly employed women. They would be incentivised to organise a network of families, to reach the target group. When this is done, they would launch specific courses for the target group which would attract the women to their facilities.

Creating a platform to exchange and offer goods/ services to alleviate the needs of staff in the (health)care sector (Action 1.7)

Background and justification

Staff from all sectors of healthcare often have needs, urgent or not, that remain unmet. A platform where these workers are brought together and can build a network based on trust and mutual respect would help in addressing these needs. This can range from purely professional needs, like a shortage of proper equipment, to needs that intersect the personal and the professional, like workers on a night shift needing a babysitter for their children.

Impacts pursued

- Easy access to (urgent) fulfilment of (health)care workers’ needs
- Building solidarity networks
- Make specific information available on various relevant topics
- Identify needs that should be handled structurally through policy initiatives

Action description

A potential pilot action to create a platform for exchanging goods and services would be best implemented in a digital space where people can exchange experiences, interact with each other, and connect with those who don’t have an extensive professional network yet. Ideally,

this platform would consist of a mobile app, as this would improve outreach to migrant communities where people tend to use mobile phones more than personal computers.

A platform like this would be very flexible: when signing up, users would have to indicate what type of worker they are (doctor, nurse, care worker, sanitation, ...) and, depending on their answer, they would get access to areas that are more specifically tailored towards them. These areas would consist of 'need' categories, where users can indicate the type of support they require: medical equipment, a job opening, day care for children, support with violence and/or harassment in the workplace, ... Because it is a 'live' platform, these categories could be updated with new ones frequently. Every 'need' category is moderated by medical staff, democratically chosen by the users, to prevent abusive situations from occurring. This should encourage a feeling of safety and more long-term participation.

It is important to plan for regional variation too and to include some sort of geolocation component into the app, allowing users from the same region to find each other. Language might pose a barrier for migrant workers, so there would preferably be a language option for English or any other widely spoken language in a certain region. Language courses might also be provided through the platform. The app should provide a special section for night-time use as well, when a lot of healthcare staff might need extra support to be able to work late-night shifts. While the development of the app can include different organisations, the app itself would be intended for individuals only and is not meant as an HR platform for companies. The app should keep a personal touch, has to be used by workers, and is supposed to promote mutual solidarity.

Target groups

Primary: Workers in the (health)care sector, including healthcare workers, hospital workers, and care workers

Secondary: (Health)care workers from (undocumented) migrant communities

Next steps

Some practical questions are still unresolved: How do we promote such a platform, especially with regards to people who are mostly outside of established structures like migrant care workers? How can such a platform be self-sustaining in the longer term? Can such a platform address worker shortages or is this too ambitious? An app such as this could be developed and maintained by a university, with sufficient input from local hospitals and (health)care professionals. Professional organisations and NGOs could also play a role, but the app would need to be adapted to each country's specific needs.

Inclusive digital leadership (Action 2.2)

Background and justification

Teleworking has brought with itself a whole new set of the challenges for companies and managers. Many managers have had to adapt to a new leadership style, one that is based on trust rather than control. Sometimes managers have found it difficult to adapt. One may be an excellent in-person manager, but absolutely not suited for remote managing.

Sometimes the difficulty to adapt to teleworking is not (only) on the managerial level, but also on the organizational level. The experience of teleworking for workers therefore can vary, depending on the company or department. Organizations and/or managers that are not well-equipped to deal with telework, could have a negative impact on employee's well-being. They could either allow teleworking but not execute it, or not approve of teleworking at all.

Impacts pursued

- Having safe and inclusive workplaces.
- Have a more diverse workforce.
- Improve health and well-being at work.

Action description

The main focus of this action would be a pilot action in the form of a workshop. The workshop would be on the topic of hybrid leadership and organization of hybrid work:

- The workshop would be co-created: workers and managers would attend the workshop together and discuss the ways in which their team can be more attentive to the needs of workers.
- The topics would range from the digital tools they use, to how they want to communicate, to how they want to organize meetings, ...
- It is important to remember that the right type of leadership and organization depends on the sector, as well as the individuals involved.

The workshop would be combined with the issuing of a set of minimal guidelines for companies regarding diversity, inclusiveness and health (physical and mental).

Realistically, the voluntary nature of the workshop and guidelines mean that their implementation is uncertain. There would therefore have to be a way to make sure that there is an impact. The following ideas were proposed:

- Link it to a certification (an award). Make this certification very attractive (can be prestige or even monetary).
- Implement an evaluation and monitoring system, devised in such a way that workers do not have to be afraid to give negative feedback.
- Let the organizer of the workshop and the evaluator/monitor be a non-profit, that does not have an incentive to create a rosy picture. This could be for example an NGO or a trade union.

- Let the implementation of guidelines be supported every step of the way by this organization.
- Note: one of the participants experienced in this field noted that businesses shove aside negative reports/findings. Therefore, there should be a way to prevent this from happening. One way could be to have recurrent check-ups so that the certification is withdrawn if there is non-compliance.

Target groups

This action addresses:

- Public organizations
- Private businesses
- Trade unions
- Civil society

A caring workspace (Action 2.5)

Background and justification

With telework, there is much less time and opportunity for co-workers to connect with one another, share their challenges, and develop a sense of belonging, care, collegiality, and even friendship.

The (often feminised) “emotional labour” that contributed to the creation of caring, supportive workspaces would often remain unnoticed, unrecognised and unpaid for before the pandemic and the prevalence of teleworking. With teleworking, its significance has hit home (organizations/corporations are finding it hard to keep their employees and people are finding it hard to receive the support and caring they need to continue working). There are also the additional challenges of physical and mental health and wellbeing that have become more widespread with the pandemic.

There is growing need to recognize such labour, acknowledge its significance and define it as a “skill” that contributes to everyone’s wellbeing - including the organization itself, as well as a need to develop mechanisms for developing a caring workspace climate.

We started with the keywords “redefining the concept of skill” which later evolved in to “a caring workspace”

The objective of the action is to:

- re-imagine organizational culture and climate as inclusive, diverse, safe and caring
- encourage organizations (companies, NGOs, schools, universities, perhaps even government offices) to design schemes for creating a caring workspace online and offline.

Impacts pursued

- Emotional labour and intelligence (often attributes claimed and practiced by women and non-normative individuals) being recognized as a skill and gift that should be encouraged and awarded
- Creating a greater sense of community, connection, belonging, collegiality, and solidarity among members of an organization (that would help alleviate prejudices and subtle forms of gender+ discrimination)
- Support the mental wellbeing of employees or members of an organization
- Contribute to sustainability
- Open space for creativity - with all stakeholders finding a caring, supportive space to express their authentic selves and create/produce with all their being
- Draw attention to new skills that are needed to organize, act and socialize in digital space
- Mitigate old/new psycho-social risks and contribute to organizational and work safety (less lost workdays due to psycho-somatic or psycho-social risks)

Action description

Three related actions are proposed:

- Designing a CHECKLIST for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace (creating an inventory of the situation to trigger reflection and action)
- Announcing a BETTER STORIES OF A CARING GENDER+ WORKSPACE AWARD (open call for organisations that have a better story of creating a caring gender+ environment in telework)
- Multisectoral and multi-size reach out (including private sectors, schools, universities, NGOs, local authorities, public)
- Designing a participatory award process which includes the use of social media where the criteria for success is defined by participants (crowdsourcing the criteria for the award: making the process participatory, transparent and universal)
- Designing a SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN that makes visible both better stories and not-so-good stories (like #metoo)

Cautionary remarks and question marks

- Social Media Campaign: Shaming is not easy for people who are still working in the organizations - how to encourage and make it safe
- Who would be excluded from a social-media campaign?
- Tools like checklists and awards already exist, but are they accessible? Are SMEs aware of them? To what extent are they gender+ and cross-sectorial? What would be our original contribution? Perhaps making these awards and checklists visible on social media could be part of the action
- part of this is again an enforcement of regulation issue: regulations OHSA are here. enforcement is a campaign issue.

Target Groups

- Companies
- NGOs
- Schools
- Universities, institutes, centres

Platform for digital training and inspiration (Action 2.6)

Background and justification

The absence of digital skills is at the basis of increased inequalities in a world of telework. Initiatives exist to facilitate the acquisition of these necessary skills to groups that risk to miss on opportunities.

Action Description

Create a European interface that brings together local/national/international initiatives for increasing digital literacy and skills from a gender+ perspective (networking, knowledge-sharing, inspiration).

Different national platforms (e.g., "[Success is Me](#)" in Poland) can be in a network where digital training is offered.

One module of this platform could be a **digital buddy**, which could manifest in different ways:

- Mentorship program – An older, more experienced employee shares wisdom with someone with more digital knowledge
- Individual can choose whether their buddy is within their organization or not
- Could also be used to draw people into the system, as sharing does not need to be 50-50 – everyone shares what they can
- Encourage employer responsibility / incentive mechanism for employer to participate in this system and encourage their employers to become active (during working hours)

Other modalities could also be introduced, for example a platform to identify needs and seek precedence or inspiration, and even organize co-creative sessions to explore solutions.

Impacts Pursued

- Inclusive / accessible everywhere and decreases inequality
- Creating solidarity across professions, generations, hierarchical roles, etc.
- Identifying and sharing better stories, to improve situations everywhere
- Contributes to efforts for more sustainable society
- Improved mental health / combat social isolation
- Improving productivity, inclusion, accessibility and connection
- Allowing previously excluded people to establish professional networks
- Empowering the individual: increasing / expanding skills
- Connecting active individuals to inspire one another and tackle ongoing issues

- Bringing together better stories of digital training for gender equality across Europe (for inspiration and possible collaboration, as well as for expanding the pool of resources offered)

Target groups

Primary: Inclusive of all individuals who are open to sharing and expanding knowledge, skills, etc.

Secondary: Employers, women in technology / STEM, employers as part of OHSA provisions in terms of mental health of employees, community organizations

Tertiary: International labour confederations to develop working models

Scalability

As an open, digital platform, the services can expand to include more modalities. It can be very crowd-driven / participatory to respond to the calls to actions by member organizations / individuals.

Toolkit for bottom-up initiatives (Action 3.1)

Background and justification

The origin of this concrete action is the need to develop more “citizen” initiatives to transform un-used public space into new green space. The trigger for the action was a better story shared by a participant on the transformation of a “back-alley” in a grey neighbourhood in Belfast into a common space to meet with the integration of nature in an area where there is no single tree.

Rather than using the term “citizen”, the group decided the action to be developed should be for bottom-up initiatives in general, not restricted to citizens only.

Many such initiatives do exist, and the focus that was chosen for the development of the action was to develop a “toolkit” that would help persons who want to launch such initiatives. Too often, these initiatives re-invent the wheel, are confronted to similar problems, which would be avoided by sharing knowledge, or accessing knowledge, expertise and experiences beforehand.

Toolkits do exist already, so the idea is to create a toolkit that links to existing toolkits filling in the gaps from an inclusivity perspective.

Impacts pursued

- Making sure the initiatives are inclusive. Empowering the initiators and developers to reach this objective.
- Create green spaces for people who have no access to green spaces
- Use the generation of new green spaces as a leverage to bring together active persons (activists in the broad sense). Green spaces as a focal point to bring together activists and network different activist people.

Action description

Scope and approach:

- Not a step-by-step guide, but rather a checklist of what should be done. This choice is made as it would be impossible to cover all the potential contexts in which such initiatives take place.
- Locally based: it is taken for granted that such initiatives are local as this is a way to ensure they will be inclusive of all residents and potential users of the space being created
- This toolkit cannot be only digital, as we want it to be inclusive.

Content:

- Identifying the challenges and potential problems, recommending ways on how to handle them
- Linking the tool with existing tools and information. Examples are toolkits using citizen-tech, guidelines on how maximise biodiversity and attract certain type of insects, bees, butterflies, ...
- Include links or information on inspiring examples
- Include recommendations on how to make the green space inclusive, bot through the process, the hardware (design, investments) and the software (what is actually happening, the use cases).

Definitions:

The toolkit should also include definitions and some principles to be applied. This is considered as a leverage to ensure inclusivity: what is a green space, what is an inclusive green space, biodiversity, gender, gender+, ...

Process of development

Making a benchmark of existing case descriptions and of existing toolkits should be an initial step in the development. Doing this benchmark would allow to identify organisations that could potentially take the responsibility to develop the toolkit.

Target groups

The ambition is to identify an organization working on gender issues at more broad level to take the lead. This organization would need to identify two grassroots organisations active in a specific neighbourhood where a public space could be transformed into a new green space. One of these organisations should be linked to LGBTQ and has to be linked to at least one other organization, preferably representing a minority or discriminated community.

Develop citizen initiatives to transform unused public space into new green spaces (Action 3.2)

Background and justification

The origin of this concrete action is the need to develop more ways to support local bottom-up initiatives to transform unused public space into new green space. Like concrete action 3.1, ('Toolkit for bottom-up initiatives'), the trigger for this particular action was a better story shared by a participant on the transformation of a 'back-alley' in a Belfast grey neighbourhood into a common space to meet with the integration of nature in an area with no green areas.

The group decided the main focus of this concrete action would be to ensure participation is inclusive of all groups which use the public space, be committed to community value building, and not crowd out groups which are usually disenfranchised (i.e., ethnic/cultural niches and minorities/those who do not speak the native language). The focus is to provide people with means to enact change themselves. With this focus, the group suggested an inclusive and participatory process which proposes and democratically selects ideas, which ideally generates a more equal distribution of green spaces in the city.

Impacts pursued

- Community value building, NOT economic-driven development
- Appropriation of the neighbourhood
- Realisation of the right to the city
- A more equal distribution of green spaces within the city
- Empowered communities
- Continuity in initiatives
- More connected multicultural neighbourhoods, which feel safer and more inclusive

Action description

Several interrelated actions were identified, all with the ambition to support local bottom-up initiatives to transform unused public space into new green spaces. Foremost, the group identified the need to **improve links** between policymakers and communities, including to connect different communities undertaking similar projects. The group emphasised the importance of **co-design** to improve local ownership.

A first step suggested was to map out and analyse the **distribution** of green space within the city to identify priority areas in need of green space and **potential areas** that can be transformed to green space.

A concrete second step/action to achieve more green space was through organizing town hall events on a '**hyperlocal**' level. Hyperlocal actions would feed into the wider strategy of

connecting to local communities that may not otherwise be involved. To connect with local communities, it was emphasised that CSOs & NGOs take part in events and process, including faith groups and new community NGOs. To succeed, groups need to be able to influence policymakers by a) creating relevant data to influence local governmental strategy, b) produce evidence-building for strategy, and c) perform training on community-led placemaking activities. Local governments should be involved at the hyperlocal level. Local governments should also ask themselves if they need training in undertaking community work. Staff members may need tools for communicating policy or strategy in a clear way to local communities.

Target groups

- CSOs, NGOs, T&As, activists
- Residents and communities in grey areas, where there is less green space
- Outreach staff (local government, depends on the work) (for skills, training and R&D)
- Students, residents, and young adults who can take ownership
- Policymakers

Programming the use of green space (Action 3.3)

Background and justification

This action was proposed as one way to create multi-purpose green spaces that tend to the needs and desires of many different groups of people. It is based on the idea of ‘hardware’ and ‘software’ for green spaces: the ‘hardware’ constitutes the green space and all of its facilities, while the ‘software’ consists of the diverse programming that can be implemented and adapted. It can be compared to the example of a cultural centre: how it programs its activities and distributes a public schedule so that users know which activities/events to expect at what times (and where). This kind of programming for green spaces, like parks, should be made in such a way as to ensure all types of users are attracted to the green space and feel welcome within its boundaries.

Impacts pursued

- Programming for different types of needs of diverse green space users
 - Also ensure space for silence, i.e., spaces without active programming at certain periods (of the day, week, year).
- Specifically targeting marginalised and excluded groups in consultation
- Combining bottom-up programming and a comprehensive, inclusive design
- Utilising arts as a tool of inclusion and promoting spaces for holistic care (including for other species)
- Example: Creating & programming spaces designed by girls/women to inspire and create a feeling of safety for other girls/women

Action description

To engage communities around green spaces like parks, the green space should be 'programmed' to a degree that attracts people, but does not exclude people either. This programming could be carried out by an NGO, but in cooperation with other organisations like a cultural/arts organisation, an environmental organisation, a sports club, a feminist organisation, etc. The legal entity managing the park (i.e., the municipality) should hold an open call through a tender process to find interested NGOs.

The selected NGO should have extensive community and professional networks in place and be familiar with the principles and practical issues of budgeting, as they would be in charge of allocating funding to the different programmed activities. The organisation in question would manage the programming by approaching other local organisations or even individuals for ideas on how to fill the green space's schedule and for the practical execution of these ideas. Any groups or individuals involved in this way should receive monetary compensation for their time and efforts. This would ensure a bottom-up approach to the programming. The managing NGO should not dictate all activities or how every area of the green space is utilised themselves, but should act as a mentor. They are, however, also subject to guidelines on diversity and inclusion, in terms of gender equality, diversity, LGBTQIA+, refugees/migrants, people with a disability, etc. They should leave certain areas within the green space free of any active programming as well, so that people can enjoy the green space on its own terms. In addition, a supervisor would make sure that all programming remains environmentally sustainable and friendly towards all species in the green space, as a condition for continued funding.

To ensure that the programming takes into account the needs of everyone, and especially vulnerable groups, a survey should identify the demographic make-up of (potential) users of the green space. In this way, the needs and desires of people living in the vicinity of the green space can be mapped and used when designing the programming, with particular attention paid to the needs of vulnerable and marginalised groups. It can also identify the reasons why certain groups of people are disproportionately not using the green space. This process can be carried out separately from the organisational activities of the NGO and can be delivered as finalised information to the NGO.

Target groups

Primary: Vulnerable groups (from a gender+ perspective) identified by a demographic survey of the community in the vicinity of the green space

Secondary: All other groups in the vicinity of the green space

Next steps

Finding urban green space owners (i.e., municipalities) who would be interested in running this initiative.

Green spaces as ecosystems of care (Action 3.4)

Background and Justification

The original challenge for this brainstorm involved programming green spaces to promote inclusive access (in terms of both time and space) and services. The conversation shifted from innovating the management of parks to evolving the way they are used, and how programmes within green spaces can promote an 'ecosystem of care' to respond to individual and community needs. Ultimately, the result could be equated to an outdoor community centre where social interaction, volunteerism and civic pride all play a role, and at-risk groups are provided a constructive environment and support.

In this context, the phrase 'ecosystem of care' includes not only personal, child or elderly care, but also intends to acknowledge and care for groups who are typically discouraged from visiting green spaces: homeless individuals, drug addicts and stray dogs, for example. It also includes the care for other natural inhabitants of green spaces, emphasizing the need to protect wild life. It also relates to democratic care in that conflict resolution is seen as an important part of ecosystems of care (i.e., conflicting perspectives are inevitable given that resources are not unlimited and needs might be in conflict).

Impacts Pursued

- Encourage use for various impacts: improve social capital, mental health, community activity, etc.
- (Positively) affect surrounding areas - fight or slow down gentrification
- Reinforce the community/collective well-being
- Ensure inclusivity of different user groups
- Promotion of inclusive action, education and holistic well-being

Action Description

Identifying how programs within green spaces can promote an ecosystem of care. Starting with small-scale prototypes that test different use cases/scenarios related to care in a temporary way. The intention is to use green space to expand the 'domestic realm' to allow these caring issues/needs to be addressed outside of the home with the help of the community using a holistic, de-segregated approach. The application of green spaces as ecosystems of care sees green spaces as changeable/evolving and that the purposes/aims of such spaces may change with the needs of surrounding/connected target groups.

Short-term steps include:

1. Research into context/gathering information to identify:
 - a. Existing/potential green spaces that could be appropriate for the creation of these prototypes
 - b. Immediate actors, needs, interests and challenges

- c. Intersections as well as conflicting needs, as conflict is inevitable in shared spaces – how can we foster productive dialogues?
2. Build alliances of care: connect groups working with stray animals, homeless, drug addicts, elderly homes, schools, etc.
3. Formulation of agenda/plan based on findings that also proposes a strategy for the collaboration between local municipalities and users
4. Communication of intentions to community, welcoming feedback or even voting on various solutions
5. Implementation: putting the prototype(s) into action, with a system to monitor and critically assess successes, challenges and other insights, as well as capture feedback from users

Long-term objective: These short-term steps can inform the creation of a greater vision, which can be evolved as more 'care ecosystem prototypes' are implemented and build on our understanding. This vision can also be informed by other pilot actions related to the theme.

Target groups

Primary: Community/users in proximity, 'friends of the park' groups or other local projects, neighbourhood groups, marginalised groups; locals who are identified as being underrepresented in park use, care organisations, education institutions, etc.

Secondary: Municipality

Scalability

The current plan of action calls for more structural/programming efforts, rather than physical interventions. This means that the program is flexible to adapt. Insights from this effort could inform more permanent or physical interventions in the future.

Ultimately, the findings and vision could be formulated as a model that could be replicated in many places (Like 'Local Agenda 2021').

The importance of greenery/green interventions (of different scales) (Action 3.5)

Background and justification

The origin of this concrete action is an identified need to develop recommendations for decision-makers to highlight/promote the importance of green spaces during a pandemic and therefore not to close parks. Parks and green spaces contribute to improved physical and mental health, which is why this initiative was developed to ensure the right balance between protection against a virus and the positive impact on (mental) health of going to green spaces.

The group identified several positive outcomes from greenery/green spaces of different scales. The importance of greenery/green was emphasised as a combination of asking WHY and HOW greenery matters. The WHY question is related to how greenery/green interventions contribute(s) to improved health, more socialising outside, local people taking ownership of parks and strengthened local government. The HOW question relates more to best practices, issues of access and the importance of lowering barriers for different groups of users to access green areas (parents with prams, disabled people, etc.). This includes the importance of space and services in green areas, as well as inclusivity and safety. In addition, greenery and green interventions needed to be of various scales, including, for example, restaurants on terraces, flower boxes, trees, and guerrilla gardening.

Impacts pursued

- Access to green spaces was anticipated to levelling out disparities, for example health (lowering probability of obesity)
- Prioritising green space in policymaking
- Reallocation of space towards green public spaces
- Overall greening of environments, so even small groups of trees, planter boxes, etc., as well as larger green spaces (parks)
- Building tolerance & understanding within community

Action description

The actions to promote the importance of greenery: green interventions (of different scales) have different steps: research, communication and connection. These steps could involve an NGO as coordinating organisation which brings insights (from research) to be communicated by locals – creators – groups – artists throughout the processes as a fourth step.

The first element is research and communication consisting of three steps. A specific connection element is related to each of the steps outlined below.

1. **Qualitative research:** asking different groups why green spaces are important to them, and how they would like to use it. This includes documenting how people have used green/public spaces throughout the pandemic (particularly vulnerable groups). In addition, document how people creatively used outdoor spaces during the pandemic.

Connection: platform/website for community-based co-planning space

2. **Construct positive narrative** that is aspirational to green interventions and emphasises the benefits of greenery including positive aspects of existing green.

Connection: workshops/hacks (gather intel and educate) that can be used as a basis to form a website/campaign.

3. **Multi-media campaign** (using local talent, i.e., performances, workshops, events, broadcasts, walking projects, etc.)

Connection: circulating better stories regarding the use of green spaces during the pandemic (videos, written stories, photo-stories, etc.)

4. As a fourth step, the coordinating organisation brings insights (from research) to be **communicated by locals** – creators – groups – artists at a citizen assembly/town hall event. This is where community feedback from workshops is presented and interactions between residents and policymakers take place.

Target groups

- Local organisations
- Friends of the park groups and neighbourhood groups
- Marginalised groups: locals who are identified as being underrepresented in park use
- Local businesses/high street (to promote material)
- People in power/elected officials, but also businesses, real estate owners, building managers
- Refugees

Gender equality policy (Action 3.6)

Background and justification

The need for a gender equality policy with regards to (the management of) green spaces grew out of the issues of improving safety in green spaces generally and reducing gender-based violence & harassment specifically. It evolved into a concrete plan that municipalities can use to improve gender equality in their public green spaces.

Impacts pursued

- Implementing an inclusive gender+ approach in municipal programs and policies around green spaces
- Promoting inclusive green spaces
- Preventing gender-based violence and harassment

Action description

Gender research organisations and other civil society organisations can develop training and implementation programs for municipal and other public authorities that cover methods of how to develop gender+ policies in the sphere of green spaces and practices. This ensures that municipalities have a gender equality policy in place (or at least an awareness of gender equality) when designing green projects and spaces. A gender equality policy like this trains municipalities on the gender+ concept, stimulates the inclusion of empathic thinking in planning processes, and could facilitate discussions on participatory processes, ensuring that

there is equal access to green spaces and to the decision-making processes around them. Tools used can include impact assessments, surveys, better stories, addressing the basics of what gender equality is with the municipality, etc. The policy would be adopted for the different steps of creating and organising green spaces, i.e., agenda-setting, planning, construction, management, maintenance, evaluation, etc. In this regard, it is also essential to include a socially sensitive public procurement checklist.

A gender equality policy would also facilitate the organisation of workshops involving multiple kinds of stakeholders on gender equality in design and decision-making with regards to green spaces. These would make use of creative methods, potentially even using the green spaces themselves as the venues for workshops (Open Studios) so that participants can see the entirety of the spaces and their shortcomings. Critical to this process is that gendered practices in the use of green spaces are addressed, which means that there needs to be gender+-aggregated data provided by the gender research organisation(s).

Target groups

The policy is carried out by gender research organisations, practitioners, and civil society organisations. It is intended for municipalities who exercise responsibility over parks, cycling routes, and other kinds of green spaces. It is ultimately to the benefit of all different kinds of green space users.

Next steps

Developing concrete training and implementation programmes and finding interested municipalities to integrate them.

Promotion of 'caring workplaces' (Action 4.1)

Background and justification

One aspect of masculinity that came to the forefront during the Open Studio is the connection between masculinity and work. Though the male breadwinner model may look outdated, the ideal of the man as the one who earns for the household is resilient. In this model, care belongs to the domestic sphere, and the man is not a carer. And workplaces currently are not caring spaces. This also has an impact, since workplaces can be women-unfriendly spaces, for example with some employers hesitating to hire women because they might be planning to get pregnant.

The idea therefore was to think about workplaces as possible spaces of care. The question was whether, rather than seeing the domain of work and care as separate spaces, we can integrate the two and create a caring workspace. The focus was on the institutional level, though there was an understanding that changes on the institutional level would probably positively impact the identity of individuals.

Impacts pursued

- Gender-empathic workplace
- Increased well-being of workers
- A reduced tension between work and other spheres of life

Action description

The action starts with identifying businesses that are pioneering in the way they organise work. The reason is that they are likely more open to this action than other actors. This business would follow a workshop with all its employees to co-create their views on what it means to be a truly caring workplace. It remains to be seen whether all businesses should be in the same workshop, or whether each business should be separate, as there may be differences between companies based on their sectors. Afterwards, the company would be asked to incorporate these views into their business policy. There would be monitoring and evaluation for a significant period of time, after which the results are published.

Part two of the action would be to create a campaign about the results to advocate for a caring workplace. This could be done through individual testimonies, as well as more general indicators of success. There would be advertisements for the campaign online and in the streets, and the option for people to give their input on it, for example through a QR code. The campaign would have to make sure it uses inclusive language and several identities.

Target groups

The main target group would be the pioneering business and its employees. Apart from them, there could be other actors that could act as allies once the results are known and a campaign around them has been created:

- Governments
- Civil society
- Trade unions
- Universities

Concrete care (Action 4.3)

Background and justification

During the first day of the OS, different ideas were expressed on the necessity to build on social solidarities that were formed during the pandemic and leverage the sense of social responsibility that emerged to recognise care as a social value. A new gender contract on gender care should be promoted as a mission of all actors (companies, trade unions, NGOs, states, individuals, etc.) and should be embedded in the rebuilding of our green society. In parallel, in earlier sessions, very concrete ideas to give more value to caring and care work

were formulated, such as more women in managerial and decision-making positions, pay recognition, compulsory parental leave and others.

During discussions on a concrete action to develop, it was highlighted that several inspiring practices exist from diverse actors; men themselves, but also NGOs or companies, and that it was worth sharing them.

The impact pursued is to raise awareness on the necessity to develop and sustain a **new gender care contract**.

Such an impact can be reached by:

- Sharing stories of individuals in care from different social groups, cultural identities, etc.
- Making men's care more visible and having men as 'role models' for each other.
- Broadening the understanding of care, not only for parents, but also relating to nature/non-humans.
- Promoting a more equal share of care work.
- Showcasing changes in the values, actions and decisions of men, e.g., men in politics involved in gender equality.

Action description

Creation of a platform (or online communication tool) to raise awareness.

The initiative is about creating a blog, a forum or any type of communication platform to share inspiring practices and tools on transforming care relations and broadening their understanding.

Access to this communication platform should be available to anyone interested, its contents will target specific groups, individuals (stories), companies and organisations (examples of work-life balance practice), policymakers (care policies), educators (teaching boys and young men in particular) and NGOs.

The platform should have different sections:

- Short and longer attractive videos on care as a central value in our society
- Information/promoting new initiatives developed within RESISTIRÉ, i.e., a programme around childbirth and promoting good care that would include men and a training for midwives on gender and masculinities (to foster men's implications)
- Facilitating access to new and existing tools.
- Link with existing podcasts such as the "Dope Black Dads" and other initiatives from diverse actors, i.e., existing gender equality plans in companies/organisations that give a central place to care in work organisation.

The content of the platform would come from the RESISTIRÉ project through the inspiring policies and practices collected and possibly also from the pilot projects (training on

childbirth). An important part of the platform would be dedicated to presentation and links to other relevant materials for the theme that are available. When operationalised, the platform can also be a tool to coordinate actions such as demonstrations and parades.

Content of the platform

- Pilot programme around childbirth for men and care professionals such as midwives.
- Concrete care stories at individual and collective level from both men and women; different sections/groups hosted in an intersectional perspective.
- Inspirational practices, stories, and tools to replicate and tailor to specific groups.
- Existing specific programmes and projects targeting boys and young men related to caring masculinities.
- Contributions to a broader understanding of care (children, elderly, environment, neighbourhood, etc.).
- Resources and contacts.
- Showcase importance of mental health issues.

It should primarily be seen as a repository of inspiring material and information on existing initiatives to reinforce visibility of care as a central value of our societies and the role of men as carers.

Scope

The group discussed the issue of the scope of the platform. Is it better to start such an initiative at the local level? An issue would be limited accessibility if it is not in English. Start with targeting a more international audience? The discussion on the scope led to the issue of languages of the platform itself, but also of materials available and the possibility to have videos with subtitles in different languages to ensure a wider dissemination.

Promoter?

Such a platform should be coordinated ideally through a bottom-up approach. An alliance of existing NGOs could be an interesting approach to coordinate such a platform (see the model of socialplatform.org).

Target groups

As mentioned above, the initiative and the platform would be accessible to anyone interested with a specific focus on the following target groups:

- Educators
- Individuals, in particular care workers in contact with fathers and men
- Companies/organisations
- Policymakers
- NGOs (to spread the information)

Links or examples of relevant material

- The educational programme “Men in Care” targeting young men and boys.
- The better story of “dope black [dads](https://dopeblackdads.com)” <https://dopeblackdads.com>
- A programme to involve fathers more in child care in [Turkey](#).

Leadership/mentoring program – Caring leadership (Action 4.4)

Background and justification:

During the first day, different ideas were expressed on the necessity to change the culture of the organisation so that care responsibilities are not seen as conflicting with work commitment. Changing the image of the ideal worker in organisational culture is crucial and can only be done if supported by the management/leadership of an organisation.

It was then highlighted that current managing values and models need to be changed. Leadership should be based on trust and integrate caring issues in management. A model of an “androgynous” and caring leadership should be developed.

The impacts pursued:

- Change work organisation in caring organisation
- Changing leadership models
- Promote self-care value within work organisations

Action description:

The initiative is about integrating care values within current leadership and mentoring programmes. Building on Covid lessons, a pilot action will be carried on developing a mentoring concept, material and resources.

The pilot project will focus on:

- Attention to workers needs, rights (e.g. to disconnect), flexible working hours, hybrid working environment.
- Type of leadership that is promoted and switching to a mix between utilitarian and expressive leadership models.
- Importance for leadership to show emotion and importance to caring aspects.
- Holistic concept of care (humans and non-humans) to be respected and implemented by leaders.

Certification of the mentoring programme?

To attract participants, the issue of what mentors and enterprises enrolling and implementing such programme in their internal mentoring scheme will get out of it. The possibility of obtaining a certification was explored.

What would be the conditions for such certification? Number of people trained? Appointing someone in the organisation? Monitoring and evaluation of the change? A number of criteria of what a caring workplace is could be developed as serve as a basis for certification.

Another way to give value to the programme is to create a community of practice.

Possible partnership

The possibility to start the project with a business school or university was raised.

The Deusto business School is working on similar management topics from a gender perspective and therefore has a relatively easy access to firms and employees if needed. In addition, the Basque Government is also working on this issue and they could be willing.

Target group:

As mentioned above, the initiative and the platform would be accessible to anyone interested with a specific focus on the following targets:

- In the first phase, employers' organisations (from both private and NGO sector). In a second phase, proposing such programme for public administration.
- Trade unions should also be involved.

Other groups of leaders can also be interested by such programme, such as political leaders.

Point of attention:

Who can give certification?

What is certified?

Terms used should not reflect gender norms such as "champion".

Educational platform on COVID-19: Care and gender roles (Action 4.6)

Background and justification

During the first day of activities, different ideas of potential training programmes were expressed for training parents, teachers, etc. Also, references were made to existing initiatives, mainly to train dads.

Impacts pursued

- The overall goal is to improve individual well-being
- A higher-level goal is to improve the status of care as COVID-19 has shown us that care deserves a higher status
- To connect people
- To help people develop skills and acquire new knowledge

Action description

Step 1: Flagship training programme

Even though the objective is to create a platform, a first step would be the organisation of a flagship training programme that would take place face-to-face.

This training should be seen as a pilot and as a way to develop content for the platform. The training would be organised for different target groups, who would be trained in homogeneous groups: students, families, HR professionals. At the end of the programme, all groups would share their experiences. During the training, which would include participative techniques, content for the platform would be co-created. Creative exercises on care and gender roles would be carried out, which would be filmed and used on the platform.

Step 2: The educational platform

The positioning of the platform would be on care and gender roles.

Its content would come from the RESISTIRÉ project through the material coming from the pilot training, but would be complemented with presentations and links to other relevant material for the theme that is available. The platform should be seen as a repository of material that can be used both by someone that wants to improve personal skills or knowledge, and by trainers and teachers who want to access educational materials they can use in their own trainings or courses.

Innovative aspects of the platform would be:

- The use of the concept of holistic care
- Intersectional in its design
- Co-created (through the flagship training)
- Both digital and physical
- Peer-driven: it would be managed as a wiki with peer review and peer input. Users can exchange experiences and help each other evaluate the potential of the material, but also exchange experiences on its use in different contexts and for different target groups.

Target groups

As mentioned above, the initiative and the platform would have two main target groups:

- Educators
- People interested in being trained: youth, families, people interested because of their professional environment (employees, managers, HR specialists, ...)

Links or examples of relevant material:

- The EU project Compass was mentioned as a benchmark for inspiration. Modules are made available for teachers about differences: “all different all equal”.

- <https://book.coe.int/en/human-rights-democratic-citizenship-and-interculturalism/7234-education-pack-all-different-all-equal-ideas-resources-methods-and-activities-for-non-formal-intercultural-education-with-young-people-and-adults-3rd-edition.html>
- An example of co-creation. One of the OS participants mentioned working on this project and trained young men to be researchers and co-delivered a training workshop to practitioners on working with BAME young fathers. Diverse Dads project: <https://cpb-eu-w2.wpmucdn.com/blogs.lincoln.ac.uk/dist/8/8374/files/2021/04/Diverse-Dads-Researching-inclusive-support-for-young-fathers-Recommendations-for-Services.pdf>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ebPoSMULI5U>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jane_Elliott
- <https://www.peaceinsight.org/en/organisations/win-peace/?location=myanmar&theme>
- The movie “I am not an easy man”
- <https://book.coe.int/en/human-rights-democratic-citizenship-and-interculturalism/7234-education-pack-all-different-all-equal-ideas-resources-methods-and-activities-for-non-formal-intercultural-education-with-young-people-and-adults-3rd-edition.html>
- <https://risemutual.org/caring-dads/>
- DigiDAD <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCkAeSuiuO3JJp71p7uxhA>

Research Agenda

Some of the action-ideas produced in the Open Studios are more of an input to feed the research agenda of RESISTIRÉ, or to be recommended for funding to Research Funding Organisations. Most of these actions have been described above, but do have a research component, or could be handled as a research project instead of a pilot action. In this case, they are not repeated, but reference is made to their descriptions in the table in the introduction of the chapter on Action-ideas above.

Urban planning (Action 2.4)

As we shift away from the 38-40-hour work week at the office, what could or SHOULD be the new normal? What is the ideal working format, and how can it influence urban planning?

Action Description

Employees have been forced to accept a 'new normal' overnight, but is this new normal an improvement on the previous situation, or could there be a BETTER new normal? Can we use this opportunity to re-define working life to evolve our habits and inspire our cities?

One step towards evolution is an assessment of physical and emotional needs to facilitate productivity, and how these needs can influence the spaces we create in future. This action suggests qualitative research that tests (combinations of) different work scenarios and monitors the resulting benefits and challenges for participants, with a focus on women.

Different scenarios have / a spectrum of productive spaces has been identified:

- Home cubicles
- Nomadic workplace – work from anywhere
- Rented desk in coworking space
- Flexible, central office / where floating desks and living amenities are available
- This could be its own initiative, where a collective of employers what they are no longer spending on offices to other services à Collective of Employers
- Fixed office space

Intended outcome

- Using this opportunity to identify a 'new normal' that improves working conditions and promotes healthier work-life relationships (and balance)
- Identify actionable needs of individuals / employees / citizens, which can translate to urban / architectural guidelines or even opportunities to stimulate projects / development

Impacts Pursued

- Addressing professional, emotional, social, health and safety needs of the individual
- Acknowledging the lives and needs of the individual, as well as their responsibilities, outside of work
- Promoting equality in the workplace, as well as at home
- Streamlining cities and spaces
- Raising the standards for professional practices
- Directing property developers - how they will develop housing

Promotion – How to 'sell' the plan?

- Could invite architect and design agencies to participate, or perhaps contribute findings themselves
- Provides PR for employer organizations who allow / encourage their employees to participate, as they would be promoting healthy work environments and considered early adopters of innovative practices
- Cities would have similar incentives as employers – actively taking part to identify the needs of their citizens

Target groups

Primary: Teleworkers

Secondary: Employers, designers, architects
Tertiary: Local and national policy leaders

Open questions/critiques of this action

- This initiative can be executed with a focus on women's needs, but can it be more inclusive of other vulnerable groups as well?
- Does this initiative do enough to address the needs of women who are not already in the teleworking system?

Lessons Learned

From this first cycle of four Open Studios, various lessons were learned regarding the OS approach, the outputs to be expected, the different exercises and materials used, and the more technical aspects of the workshop organisation. Overall, the approach developed for the Open Studios worked very well, with participants often being enthusiastic at the end of an OS. From the perspective of the RESISTIRÉ project, the Open Studios delivered results according to expectations. In the final sharing, the external (invited) participants expressed their appreciation of the Open Studio method (especially for providing an inclusive space for participation and co-creation), some saying that they want to use it in their own work and organisation, others asking for the Open Studio methodology to be developed into a pilot action itself.

The flow worked very well with regard to all four groups and themes: the first two sessions (first morning) of the OS worked to create a cohesive group and to involve all participants. The next two sessions (first afternoon) allowed us to have further discussions and, at the same time, to direct these discussions and the participants' reflections towards potential solutions. In all four Open Studios, the production of potential action-ideas at the end of the first day proved more than sufficient to launch the programme of the second day. The method to select ideas at the start of the second day's activities was adapted slightly after OS1 and worked very smoothly as well. This is important as this session remains a critical step in the whole process. The main conclusion is that the overall approach can be maintained for future Open Studios, although some interesting lessons can be learned.

There was, for instance, some hesitation regarding the duration when defining the approach. The concept as foreseen in the grant agreement provided for two full days in a face-to-face setting. It was decided to keep the principle of two full days, even though we had initially foreseen to spread the OS over more days in case it was held online. This decision seemed to be a good one, as very few participants (3/80+) mentioned explicitly that the duration was too long. The overall consensus seemed to be that the rhythm was intense but feasible, given the fact that the timing was respected. One of the concrete ways to boost participants' energy levels was the use of two brief qigong sessions (two 15-minute sessions at the start of sessions 4 and 8). They were used in three of the four Open Studios (starting with the second one, responding to the need identified in OS1) and are proposed to be maintained in the future.

Regarding the choice of OS themes, one of them focused on a specific target group (healthcare workers), while the other three worked around specific themes. Both approaches worked, so there is no need to have a preferred approach in the future. As for the technical choice of using a combination of Zoom and Miro, Miro can be somewhat intimidating at first, although most participants were able to use it adequately by the end of the first day of activities. To ensure that everyone is using Miro, however, it is imperative that participants

don't call in from their phones, but are using a desktop or laptop and that a briefing session is organised just before the start of the OS.

In general, there was a balanced mix of invited participants and consortium members. The makeup of the invited participants was generally balanced as well, though more people from the target groups themselves could have been involved (especially in the case of OS1) and, for some of the Open Studios, there could have been more people with creative/artistic backgrounds.

Reflecting on the use of better stories, this technique worked really well to launch discussions, to create a group feeling, and to instigate creative thinking. Concerning the use of personas, deciding on the specific mix of personas is a critical step as they set the scene and launch reflections and discussions. However, participants only rarely developed the provided persona stories further. This can be addressed either through the efforts of the facilitator – stimulating the further development and adaptation of the story – or by making the personas less detailed. This could be tested in future Open Studios.

Finally, looking back on the output for the WP6 tasks, the Open Studios have produced a sizeable number of action-ideas for operationalisation. Regarding the future research agenda, we had anticipated to identify open questions that could lead to research questions, but not that concrete actions could potentially be (small) research projects, as seems to be the case now.

Conclusion

The results of the research activities performed in RESISTIRÉ during the first cycle have shown that “COVID-19 and its policy responses have made the most vulnerable even more vulnerable, with strong gender regimes and social class and social capital regimes cutting across multiple domains” (Axelsson et al. 2021). The Open Studios have shown that this negative trend creates an opportunity as it emphasises the need for change. The situation became worse for many vulnerable groups due to the pandemic and the policy responses associated with it, but this has made the inequalities more visible as well. There is no excuse anymore not to act.

Most of the action-ideas produced through the Open Studios were triggered by what happened during the lockdowns and the different waves of the pandemic, but the final results encompass solutions to tackle the root causes of the inequalities, even after the end of the pandemic. The solution directions proposed are holistic and cut across policies. They seldomly address public health policymaking directly.

The Open Studios are one step in the RESISTIRÉ process: from research to insights to solutions to piloting those solutions and to advocating change based on evidence. It is a short but critical step in that process whereby actual impact and conclusions will become visible in the next stages. As this was the first cycle and, thus, constituted a first experience with this specific format of Open Studios within this domain, it is interesting to formulate conclusions on the approach itself.

The interdisciplinary dimension of the approach has clearly contributed to more and better insights. Researchers from the project confronted their own insights with those of experts of the specific theme of the OS, as well as with users. The more creative profiles present in the OS helped to think out of the box and look at the value of interventions that were eye-opening for some participants. The contribution to the development of solutions is limited to a first step and, in particular, the more innovative ideas need further development. Nevertheless, the Open Studios proved to be a valuable method in that they gradually change the focus from research to action and solutions.

The OS format allows us to make use of the expertise available in the OS and we should exploit this richness as much as possible. All ideas have to be further developed making use of the expertise available within the consortium and additional expertise, particularly user expertise. Although ‘users’ were present in all OS, the conclusion is that there is a need for more user involvement. As there are barriers to include more users in the format of the OS, the way forward could be to have workshops with users before and/or after the OS: before to feed the OS with user-based insights, and after to further develop and validate action-ideas developed in the OS. Barriers to involving users in the OS are the time (it was, for example,

very difficult to recruit healthcare workers for two full days) and the sensitivity to recruiting participants from vulnerable groups.

The better stories proved to be a helpful new tool in having the experts critically assess existing policies and societal initiatives, without immediately proposing unattainable goals/solutions. They allowed the experts to be inspired by the positive aspects of an existing policy/initiative and made them think about how to improve those aspects to make them more inclusive for vulnerable groups and to target existing inequalities in a more effective way. Overall, the better stories and the initial discussion around them enhanced the imaginative and inclusive nature of the pilot actions.

References

- Axelsson, TK., Callerstig, A-C., Sandström, L., & Strid, S. (2021). RESISTIRE D4.1 Qualitative indications of inequalities produced by COVID-19 and its policy responses. 1st cycle summary report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5595815>.
- Bonaccorsi, G., Pierri, F., Cinelli, M., Porcelli, F., Galeazzi, A., Flori, A., Pammolli, F., (2020). Economic and social consequences of human mobility restrictions under COVID-19. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Cibin, R., Stöckelová, T., Linková, M. (2021). *RESISTIRE D2.1 - Summary Report mapping cycle 1*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361042>.
- Cumming, C., Wood, L., & Davies, A. (2020). People experiencing homelessness urgently need to be recognised as a high-risk group for COVID-19. *Health Promotion Journal of Australia*. Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Lewnard, J. A., & Lo, N. C. (2020). Scientific and ethical basis for social-distancing interventions against COVID-19. *The Lancet. Infectious disease*.
- Lokot, M., & Avakyan, Y. (2020). Intersectionality as a lens to the COVID-19 pandemic: implications for sexual and reproductive health in development and humanitarian contexts. *Sexual and Reproductive Health Matters*, 28:1.
- Lombardo, E., & Kantola, J. (2019). European integration and disintegration: Feminist perspectives on inequalities and social justice. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 57(S1), 62–76.
- Nicola, M., Alsafi, Z., Sohrabi, C., Kerwan, A., Al-Jabir, A., Iosifidis, C., & Agha, R. (2020). The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: a review. *International Journal of Surgery*.
- Sciensano. (2020). *COVID-19 Epidemiologische situatie*.
- Van Bavel, J. J., Baicker, K., Baggio, P. S., Capraro, V., Cichocka, A., Cikara, M., & Drury, J. (2020). Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1-12.
- Verloo, M. (2013). Intersectional and cross-movement politics and policies. *Signs*, 38(4), 893–915.
- Walby, S. (2015). *Crises*. Bristol: Polity Press.
- Walby, S., Armstrong, J., & Strid, S. (2012). Intersectionality. Multiple tensions in social theory. *Sociology*, 46(2), 224–240.
- Walter, L. A., & McGregor, A. J. (2020). Sex- and gender-specific observations and implications for COVID-19. *The Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*. NLM Medline.

Annex

Generic Guideline

OPEN STUDIOS – Creating better stories

In Open Studios, we will be exploring the possibilities for co-creating better stories of responding to the pandemic. What have been some inspiring practices, initiatives, policies that we have observed in different contexts across Europe? What can we learn from them to imagine even better stories of responding to this crisis that we all share, but are not equally affected by? How can a gender+ perspective help us explore, make visible and co-create more egalitarian, more inclusive policies, initiatives and practices? As feminist scholar Dina Georgis argues in her book *The Better Story*, "there is always a better story than the better story."

This Open Studio will enable a co-creative setting where we will learn from the existing better stories of responding to the pandemic in more inclusive ways and co-design even better stories together.

OS(#) – Better is possible: (Insert Title)

This Open Studio has to contribute to following objectives:

- Translate the results of the research activities into insights.
- Develop ideas of potential actions and solutions to:
 - (Describe challenges here)
- Critically assess these ideas in terms of impact and feasibility.

Material to be sent in advance to participants

- A general briefing on the RESISTIRÉ project;
- A set of promising practices (better stories) corresponding to the theme of the OS (both policy and societal responses);
- Highlights of the RESISTIRÉ deliverables on the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on inequalities (with a specific section dedicated to the theme of the OS).

What to ask participants before the OS:

- To register and try out Miro in order to familiarize themselves with the digital whiteboard, including to have a look at who the other participants are (alternative is to organise a briefing session beforehand);
- Any examples of promising practices corresponding to the theme of the OS (both policy and societal responses).

What to prepare and have available during the OS:

- Personas
- PPT on issues linked to (open studio theme)

DAY 01

Session 01 – Warmup & Getting Started – 9:15-10:30

9:15-9:30 – Participants are welcomed and given brief introduction to RESISTIRÉ project.

9:30-9:45 – Participants are divided into groups of two, who will introduce themselves to each other through ‘our better stories’.

- Who are they? Based where? Doing what?
- Positive experience from Covid; positive change (personal better story)?
- Positive experience resulting from a policy or initiative related to the OS theme (better story related to theme)?

Rapporteur puts all participants in rooms by two (random)

9:45-10:15 – Participants return to plenary, introduce their conversation partners and their respective answers to the above questions.

10:15-10:30 – General discussion about what was heard, what personal experiences in different contexts tell us about pandemic’s impact, what better stories are possible. Also pay attention to the common characteristics of our better stories and who/what institutions have helped enable them.

All participants are invited to meet on Miro. Short intro to make sure all are at the same place. One of the co-facilitators is the active listener and asks questions/clarifications if needed, also goes to the next duo and acts as timekeeper. The other co-facilitator is writing on the poster.

15-minute break

Session 02 – Inspiration – 10:45-13:00

10:45-10:55 – Presentation about inequalities created and/or deepened during pandemic related to theme.

10:55-11:15 – In plenary, sharing of participants’ knowledge and experiences & discussion of the basic questions and observations behind the OS.

11:15-12:15 – Participants split into 4 smaller groups which each receive a set of policy responses and a set of societal responses. Groups should spend approximately the same amount of time on both sets and process at least one of each (preferably two or even more) by identifying on a poster:

- What makes the policy/societal initiative a positive one?
- Which aspects of the policy/societal initiative could be improved?

12:15-12:45 – Participants return to plenary, present their results and review the findings of the other groups. Important points of focus are the common characteristics between policies/initiatives and what actors, institutions, resources, etc. have contributed to these policies/initiatives.

12:45-13:00 – Remaining in plenary, participants identify what/who is missing in the existing better stories & who is still excluded and could benefit from further inclusion.

60-minute lunch break

Session 03 – Empathy – 14:00-15:15

14:00-14:50 – Participants are split into 4 smaller groups which are assigned two personas each. They should identify what circumstances, policies, societal initiatives and/or other factors would have made a difference for the specific issues of these personas. Their answers are captured on a poster with pre-defined issues as per the presentation in session 02. Participants should spend maximum 30 minutes on one persona.

14:50-15:15 – Participants return to plenary where they share their findings. This enables them to identify any additional gaps and opportunities/ideas for future action.

15-minute break

Session 04 – Brainstorm (1) – 15:30-17:00

15:30-15.45 – Qi gong with music & reflection on how participants feel/how it felt to move the body (in chat).

15.45-16:30 – Participants are split into 4 small groups and start brainstorming with the help of a lotus blossom. Brainstorm should look at the barriers present from the perspective of socioeconomic inequalities (which are placed beforehand in the lotus blossom) and how the participants can develop ideas on how to overcome those barriers.

Barriers/questions:

- [\(Describe OS-specific barriers/questions here\)](#)

16:30-16:50 – Participants return to plenary to share their findings.

16:50-17:00 – Remaining in plenary, participants reflect once again on what/who has been missing from the discussion and what groups of people would not be able to benefit from the ideas that were brought up.

DAY 02

Session 05 – Brainstorm (2) – 9:15-10:30

9:15-9:20 – What is your internal weather like right now? What was for you the “highlight” or the “better story” of yesterday’s Open Studio? (write in chat, share with everyone when prompted by the facilitator).

9:20-10:30 – In plenary, facilitators present a long list of ideas from day 1 that could be developed in day 2. The context of RESISTIRÉ is explained again: concrete actions need to be developed that improve the situation of vulnerable groups. These can be: recommendations (to policymakers, employers, NGOs); or actions that could be piloted/tested during the project.

The list proposed is challenged by the participants: what is missing, what can be merged, what can be split?

During this discussion, co-facilitators are copy-pasting the ideas for action in a lotus-blossom type of poster on the right side. They are adding sticky notes characterising the idea based on the discussion (in another colour).

When the list has been discussed, all participants move to the right on the Miro board to look at the lotus blossom poster.

The facilitator now goes through all the ideas one by one and asks the participants to choose two ideas they think we should be working on: they fit RESISTIRÉ, it is feasible to characterise them more during the day and they are interested in working on them.

- Selection of participants to work in small groups can happen at the end of this session or at the start of the next session depending on timing.

Longer 30-minute break to allow facilitation team to select the ideas to be worked on in further sessions

Session 06 – Co-create (1) – 11:00-12:30

11:00-11:30 – Participants are split in smaller self-selected groups which are assigned one idea from the list of ideas compiled by the facilitation team during the break. Participants should start with a brief brainstorming exercise to identify any additional elements that could enhance the impact of the initial idea. There is a standard poster with proposed dimensions to be considered for the brainstorm; but these can be changed depending on the idea, both by the facilitators, or by the group.

11:30-12:00 – Participants, still in smaller groups, fill in a poster with basic information for a societal response that could lead to a pilot action and/or to recommendations for stakeholders.

At the end of the session, the facilitator asks to identify “open questions”, that could be included in the next research cycle.

12:00-12:30 – Participants return to plenary where all of the results are reviewed and participants are encouraged to add questions, comments and/or suggestions next to the group posters.

60-minute lunch break

Session 07 – Co-create (2) – 13:30-15:00

13:30-14:00 – Participants are split in smaller self-selected groups which are assigned another idea from the list of ideas compiled by the facilitation team during the break. Participants should start with a brief brainstorming exercise to identify any additional elements that could enhance the impact of the initial idea.

14:00-14:30 – Participants, still in smaller groups, fill in a poster with basic information for a policy response that could lead to a pilot action and/or to policy recommendations. At the end of the session, the facilitator asks to identify “open questions”, that could be included in the next research cycle.

14:30-15:00 – Participants return to plenary where all of the results are reviewed and participants are encouraged to add questions, comments and/or suggestions next to the group posters.

15-minute break

Session 08 – Conclusions – 15:15-17.00 (recorded session)

15:15-15:30 – Qi gong with light music & reflection on how participants feel in chat.

15:30-16:15 – All individual participants are asked to share their conclusions one by one with the group on which ideas they consider have the highest potential to be developed further and implemented by RESISTIRÉ (target is to choose two ideas). Participants explain why this is their choice.

This time can also be used to:

- Include an unplanned session triggered by the results of the previous sessions.
- Add further details to some of the most promising ideas identified (i.e., a strong candidate for a concrete pilot action).

This discussion is run on Zoom, but co-facilitators are capturing what is being said on a poster on Miro which is shared with the group at the end of the discussion. This poster captures: the reasons for the choice, the hesitations expressed as well as the votes (choice for actions).

16:15-16:45 – Participants are asked what experiences they take away from the Open Studio, what their recommendations would be for future Open Studios and what they would recommend for the RESISTIRÉ project as a whole.

